

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A572

19 August 1997

TACIA

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 572

DATE: 19/08/97

Take off: 1250

Landing: 2020

Aircraft Scientist : H RICHER
 Flight Leader : D PERCIVAL
 Others 2D : D ARTHUR
 CNC, PSAP/H₂O₂ : K DEWEY
 PAN ECOC : S KENT
 BOTTLES : D FINDLEY
 H₂O₂ : B BANDY
 NOXT : S BAGQUITTE
 FORMALDEHYDE : G MILLS
 CO : S SCHMITZEN
 PERCA : T GREEN
 PROJECT SCIENTISTS { S PENHETT
 L DAVIES
 K LAW

Captain : SQN LDR C O'BRIEN
 Co-pilot : FLT LT M PURSE
 Navigator : SQN LDR S AYLES
 Engineer : FLT SGT M LIENNAOS
 Loadmaster : M ALM K CROSS

Trials Instructions TACIA MRF1 :

Operating area : ENGLISH CHANNEL, NORTH SEA, ST. GEORGES CHANNEL

General synoptic situation

TIME: 12Z

A572 19-AUG-97

12:53:00-20:17:10GMT

INS TRACK - run no

A572 19-AUG-97 Height time series

A572, 19th August, 1997
TACIA & WARM FRONT
English Channel, Southern North Sea, St.Georges Channel.

Start time	End time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
125250					Take off RAF Lyneham
130017			3000'	220°	Instrument warm up leg.
130242	132530	R1	FL080	230°	
132530	133435	P1	FL080 50 ft	175°/100°	500fmp from 2000' Sea State 1
133452	133752	R2	100'	100°	Saw Tooth 1 UP
133752	133929	P2	100'- 800'	100°	500fpm
133929	134203	R3	800'	100°	
134203	134343	P3	800'- 2000'	110°	500fpm
134343	134738	R4	2000'	100°	
134738	134941	P4	2000'- 4000'	100°	1000fpm
134941	135206	R5	4000'	100°	
135206	135302	P5	4000'- 5000'	100°	1000fpm
135302	135520	R6	5000'	100°	Saw Tooth 1 DOWN
135520	135620	P6	5000'- 4000'	100°	1000fpm
135620	135945	R7	4000'	100°	
135945	140148	P7	4000'- 2000'	100°	1000fpm
140148	140339	R8	2000'	100°	
140339	140531	P8	2000'- 800'	055°	500fpm
140531	140713	R9	800'	055°	
140713	140907	P9	800'- 50 ft	055°	500fpm Sea state 1
140907	141104	R10	100'	055°	Saw Tooth 2 UP
141104	141229	P10	100'- 800'	055°	500fpm
141229	141353	R11	800'	055°	
141353	141554	P11	800'- 2000'	055°	500fpm
141554	141717	R12	2000'	050°	
141717	141848	P12	2000'- 3500'	050°	1000fpm
141848	142040	R13	3500'	050°	
142040	142205	P13	3500'- 5000'	055°	1000fpm
142205	142616	R14	5000'	055°	Saw Tooth 2 DOWN
142616	142742	P14	5000'- 3500'	050°	1000fpm
142742	143322	R15	3500'	050°	
143322	143451	P15	3500'- 2000'	070°	1000fpm
143451	143631	R16	2000'	070°	
143631	143841	P16	2000'- 800'	070°	500fpm
143841	144015	R17	800'	070°	
144015	144203	P17	800'- 50 ft	070°	500fpm Sea state 1
144223	144402	R18	100'	070°	Saw Tooth 3 UP
144402	144537	P18	100'- 800'	070°	500fpm
144537	144728	R19	800'	070°	
144728	144937	P19	800'- 2000'	070°	500fpm
144937	145102	R20	2000'	070°	
145102	145232	P20	2000'- 3500'	070°	1000fpm
145232	145552	R21	3500'	070°	
145552	145726	P21	3500'- 5000'	030°	1000fpm
145726	145949	R22	FL050	030°	Saw Tooth 3 DOWN
145949	150249	P22	FL050- 2000'	030°	1000fpm
150249	150435	R23	2000'	030°	
150435	150632	P24	2000'- 800'	030°	500fpm
150632	150809	R24	800'	030°	
150809	150945	P25	800'- 50 ft	030°	500fpm Sea state 3

150955	151132	R25	100'		030°	Saw Tooth 4 UP
151132	151307	P26	100' - 800'		030°	500fpm
151307	151453	R26	800'		030°	
151453	151717	P27	800' - 2000'		035°	500fpm
151717	151902	R27	2000'		035°	
151902	152040	P28	2000' - 3500'		040°	1000fpm
152040	152235	R28	3500'		040°	
152235	152422	P29	3500' - FL050		015°	1000fpm
152422	152657	R29	FL050		055°	Saw Tooth 4 DOWN
152657	152832	P30	FL050 - 3500'		045°	1000fpm
152832	153020	R30	3500'		045°	
153020	153148	P31	3500' - 2000'		040°	1000fpm
153148	153335	R31	2000'		040°	
153335	153617	P32	2000' - 800'		040°	500fpm
153617	153816	R32	800'		040°	
153816	154011	P33	800' - 50 ft		040°	500fpm Sea state 3
154114	154249	R33	100'		010°	Saw Tooth 5 UP
154249	154419	P34	100' - 800'		005°	500fpm
154419	154636	R34	800'		005°	
154636	154852	P35	800' - 2000'		005°	500fpm
154852	155122	R35	2000'		005°	
155122	155254	P36	2000' - 3500'		280°	1000fpm
155254	160030	R36	3500'		270°	
160030	160158	P37	3500' - 5000'		275°	1000fpm
160158	160722	R37	5000'		260°	Saw Tooth 5 DOWN
160722	160854	P38	5000' - 3500'		275°	1000fpm
160854	161115	R38	3500'		270°	
161115	161247	P39	3500' - 2000'		275°	1000fpm
161247	161417	R39	2000'		275°	
161417	161631	P40	2000' - 800'		275°	500fpm
161631	161803	R40	800'		275°	
161803	161952	P41	800' - 50 ft		270°	500fpm Sea state 2
162004	162156	R41	100'		280°	Saw Tooth 6 UP
162349	162525	P42	100' - 800'		165°	500fpm
162525	162740	R42	800'		165°	
162740	163007	P43	800' - 2000'		160°	500fpm
163007	163118	R43	2000'		160°	
163118	163255	P44	2000' - 3500'		165°	1000fpm
163255	163551	R44	3500'		165°	
163551	163720	P45	3500' - 5000'		170°	1000fpm
163720	163904	R45	5000'		170°	Saw Tooth 6 DOWN
163904	164037	P46	5000' - 3500'		165°	1000fpm
164037	164742	R46	3500'		165°	
164742	164913	P47	3500' - 2000'		165°	1000fpm
164913	165046	R47	2000'		165°	
165046	165311	P48	2000' - 800'		165°	500fpm
165311	165456	R48	800'		165°	
165456	165701	P49	800' - 50 ft		180°	500fpm Sea state 21
165709	165835	R49	100'		180°	
WARM FRONT						
170010	171955	P50	50 ft - FL100		275°	1000fpm from 1000'
172418	174056	R50	FL100		235°	Daventy corridor
174056	175913	climb	FL100 - FL240		300°	Climb to recce front.
181123	182558	R51	5000'		220°	Run thru warm front.
182820	184948	R52	1000'		220°/280°	Run thru warm front.
185026	190043	R53	1000'		270°	
190426	193109	R54	5000'		045°	Run thru warm front.
193935	194609	R55	FL080		050°	Run thru warm front.

201715

Land at RAF Lyneham

TACIA August 1997

Flight A572

19/08/97

OBJECTIVE: To measure chemical composition of polluted plumes at different locations from northern Europe and, weather permitting, investigate transport associated with warm fronts.

LOCATION: North Sea.

WEATHER: Avoid areas of cloud and precipitation where possible.

SAMPLING PATTERN

Part A: Continental Pollution

1. Take-off Lyneham 11:00 local time.
2. Ascend to 3000ft and hold for 5 minutes for chemical instrumentation.
3. Transit to sampling area at or above FL100 (>15 minutes).
4. Profile from FL100 at 500ft/min to minimum safe altitude.
5. Stepped sawtooth run between 50ft and 5000ft parallel to the coast of France, Belgium, the Netherlands and Germany: (50N, 2E) to (54N, 6E)
6. Continue sawtooth in a westward direction to a point off the UK coast (53N, 2E).
7. Turn to further continue sawtooth run into the wind *ca.* 50 miles.

Part B: Warm Front

8. Transit in direction of warm front *- SATCOM FOR POS OF FRONT.*
9. Ascend to FL200.
10. Cross frontal surface at three heights : FL200, FL125 and 5000ft, see Figure. *→ WAVE.*
11. Return to Lyneham.

OTHER REQUIREMENTS: Constant cabin pressure on level runs. Communications with TACIA Ops. required (SATCOM or phone patch).

Part A: Continental Pollution

Part B: Warm Front

Side view: Vertical Structure

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A572 Date: 14 08 97 User: TAKIA
Interactive by: D PERCIVAL
Date: 20 08 97

Renav

KALMAN FILTERING USED.

TWC

Profile plotted :

Line chosen : Profile / Whole flight \ Other

a = - 0.2722 E+1

b = + 0.3876 E-2

c = + 0.1712 E-6

LWC

PMS DATA FOR ONLY PART OF FLIGHT

Heimann / Barnes

OK

AIRCRAFT FLYING PROGRAMME

DATE 19 August 1997

FLIGHT NO A572

FTI MRF1 TACIA

Aircraft scientist	H Richer	NOxy	S Bauguitte	
Flight leader	D Percival	Peroxide	B Bandy	WENDY DAVIS (SERG)
Cloud physics	D Arthur	Formaldehyde	G Mills	
CCN/PSAP/Oz	K Dewey	CO	S Schmitgen	
Pan ECGC	J Kent	PERCA	T Green	
Bottles	D Findley	Project Scientists X 2		Stuart Parkett Hathy Law

Pre-flight clearance D Arthur / D Findley dep 0715

FTOs Depart F'boro 0715

Briefing 0900 Take off 1100 Land at 1900
Lyneham

Press RETURN for next display (H for help)

NEXT DAY 18-AUG-1997 16:32

14
5

19 103

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: ~~████~~ 572 Date: ~~████████~~ 140897 A/S Name: ~~████████~~ RICHETZ

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for 3 at least
2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period INDEF
3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project ... TACIA
4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long? INDEF
5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?
6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in? TBD
7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

Flight No: A572 Date: 190297

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CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0953	REF +	5	567	✓		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2853	✓		Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19	4095	F/S O/S	TORQUE 4.0	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	4095	F/S O/S	TORQUE 3.0	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	0000			As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	3261	1000	1001	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3296	1000	/		
	A/S	9	0093	/		As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	965	285	279		
	UP2S	82	773	125	141		
	UIRS	83	352.	-330	3NO2		
	UP1Z	84	152	/		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	149	✓		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	415	✓ 155P	3NO2	Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2301	26.	26.3	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2313	26		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0000		3NO2	As IAT	
	LP1S	91	256	42	56		
	LP2S	92	281	35	37		
	LIRS	93	0042		3NO2		
	LP1Z	94	151	/		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	154	/		Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	0034	✓	3NO2	Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2303	26.		As IAT	
	LP2T	98	226P	26	27	As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0000		3NO2	As IAT	
	J/W	42	906			As Indicated 0000	
	HYGR	58	3109	20.4	20.7		
	HYCC	59	726	/		696-901	
	FDEW	138	4095			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	4095				
	DTF	10	3200	28	28.7		
	DTC	11	6	IAT	27.3		
	NDTF	23	3563	30	26.0	same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	6				
	INCT	48	0346				
	HEIM	141	3230	29.0			
	PRTC	142	2324	16		approx 2380	
	TWCD	70	3257	/		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	233	/		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	156				
	O3P	106	2034	958	/	P ≈ (DRSU × 0.4) + 145mB	
	O3RG	113	1823				
0419							

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
0919	FL NO	1	Hex	0572	4572	/	Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0092	/		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0D12	/		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	9			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
				0000	too	H/d	?
	LATC	160	Dec	0000			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	0000			Longitude
0922							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: PRE FLIGHT.

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70	5290	/		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	1325	/		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	239	/		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2628	/		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2274	/		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2076	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2122	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1022	/		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4084	/		4095	
	EV1V	170	2043				
	EV2V	171	2043				
	NPWR	172	3310				
	EVIC	173	3968				
0925	EV2C	174	3968				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

Flight No: 572

Date: 190897

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CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1414	REF +	5	567	✓		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2852	✓		Approx 2858	
1424	AOSS	19	1871	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1008	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	4095	5000 ^{min}	✓	As Indicated	0000
	PR HT	8	3268	5.0	✓	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	2900	911	✓		
	A/S	9	1294	179	✓	As ASI	0000 - 0100
1511	UP1S	81	1491	448	502		
	UP2S	82	1300	44231	264		
	UIRS	83	568	-280	3N02		
	UP1Z	84	152	✓		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	151	✓		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	667		3N02	Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2466	18	20.3	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2474			As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0000		3N02	As IAT	
	LP1S	91	211	20	36		
	LP2S	92	210	14	14		
1614	LIRS	93	104		3N02		
	LP1Z	94	149	✓		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	151	✓		Approx 0146	
1648	LIRZ	96	143	✓	3N02	Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2458	19		As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2423	20	21.7	As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0000		3N02	As IAT	
1705	J/W	42	1350	0.1	0.12	As Indicated	0000
	HYGR	58	2578	3.0	-1.6		
	HYCC	59	807	✓		696-901	
	FDEW	138	2006	0	0 ✓	DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	608				
	DTF	10	3425	15	7.2		
	DTC	11	5		13.8		
	NDTF	23	3472	14	5.9	same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	5				
	INCT	48	2297	✓			
	HEIM	141	2842	20	✓		
	PRTC	142	2383	16		approx 2380	
	TWCD	70	1007	✓		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	1130	✓		0640-1860	< min
	O3	100	190	✓			
	O3P	106	1852	885.8		$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	2161				
1715							

Flight Leaders' Pre-In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1716	FL NO	1	Hex	572	/		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0171	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0648	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0126	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
2821 0.	3856 1260	2816	899	2818	3734	2798	174
	LATC	160	Dec	596	52.448M	/	Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	0002	0.17 E	/	Longitude
1721							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: FL100

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1732	TWCD	70	1455	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2551	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1090	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2632	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2232	/		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2079	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2852	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1020	/		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095			4095	
	EV1V	170	3487				
	EV2V	171	3145				
	NPWR	172	2672				
	EVIC	173	4004				
1740	EV2C	174	4001				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1829	FL NO	1	Hex	0572	✓		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0183	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0024	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	134	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
3542 19.8	146P ✓ 3856 ✓	3541	573	3540	371P	358P	139
	LATC	160	Dec	0589	51.832		Latitude
	LONG	161	Dec	4031	-5.272		Longitude
1833							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: 10000ft

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1834	TWCD	70	2921	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2574	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1215	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2832	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2252	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	3502	✓	Noise + ?	0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2172	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1022	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	3491				
	EV2V	171	3144				
	NPWR	172	2658				
	EVIC	173	4004				
1840	EV2C	174	4007				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

Flight No: A572

Date: 14 08 97

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CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1750	REF +	5	567	/		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2852	/		Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19	2075	F/S - O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1366	F/S - O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	4045	✓	F4240.	As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	1514	24.0	FL240 ✓	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	2490	750.			
	A/S	9	1268	178		As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	0886	250	237		
	UP2S	82	0664	108	114		
	UIRS	83	353	-330	JN02		
	UP1Z	84	152	✓		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	134	✓		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	250	✓	JN02	Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2768	4	17.5	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2750	4		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0500		JN02	As IAT	
	LP1S	91	0216	25	56		
	LP2S	92	0139	-6	11		
	LIRS	93	0064	✓	JN02		
	LP1Z	94	134	✓		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	135	✓		Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	0844		JN02	Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2538	15	18.2	As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2526	16		As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0200		JN02	As IAT	
	J/W	42	1460	0.3	0-18	As Indicated 0000	
	HYGR	58	2738	17			
	HYCC	59	712	✓		696-901	
	FDEW	138	2113	5.65	-13.7	DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	0608				
	DTF	10	0426	17	-8.8		
	DTC	11	6		17.6		
	NDTF	23	376	17	-10.0	same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	6				
	INCT	48	2623				
	HEIM	141	2568	11	/		
	PRTC	142	2383	/		approx 2380	
	TWCD	70	2240	/		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	1172	/		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	068				
	O3P	106	1704			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	2065				
1826							

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 572.....

Date 19 08 97.....

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Video Tape	
No.	Ends 1550
(FFC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	51° 30.28N	51° 30.30W
Long	001° 59.10W	001° 59.10W
Time	0847	0848
Status	OK	GC ALGN.

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y / n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y / n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	☒ y / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
075344				DATA ON					
123045				Set to Nav					
12520				Take off RAF Lyneham					
				Climb level 3000ft					
130217	10	3000	1001	220	180	15.4	10.1	off	160/6.
				CONTINENTAL POLLUTION					
				START RUN 1					
130242	11	FLO60	1013	225	180	11.5	8.0	off	163/10.
				INT RI					
130501	12	FLO60	1013	225	180				
				Restart RI					
130734	13	FLO80	1013	230	180	8.1	1.2	OFF	179/7.
				Cont RI					
132530	14	FLO80	1013	175	180	8.0	6.1	OFF	184/7
				ABSENT INT PI					
133055	15	2000ft		000	180	20.6	15.4		
				End PI					
133301									SS = 1
133435	17	500ft	1018	100	180	14.3	15.8	OFF	144/3

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 572.....

Date 19.08.97.....

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Video Tape	
No. #1	
Ends 1550	
FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	50° 00.08N	50° 00.43N
Long	00° 43.81W	00° 41.01 W
Time	1358.41	1359.08.
Status	07	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y) n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr		Wind/ Sea st.
				End	R7	1st	P7			
135445	29	4000	101P	100	145	140		OFF		
				End	P7	1st	R8			
140148	30	2000	101P	100	180	22.7	10-6	OFF		149/8.
				End	R8	1st	P8	500 FPM.		
140334	31	2000	101P					OFF		/
				End	P8	1st	R9			
140531	32	1000	101P	055	180	24.9	13.2	OFF		106/5
				End	R9	1st	P9			
140713	33	800	101P	055	180			OFF		/
				End	P9	1st	R10	-10		8=1
140907	35	500ft	101P	055	180	21.3	16.5	OFF		080/7
				End	R10	1st	P10			
141104	36	100ft	101P	055	180	23.8	13.5	OFF		085/6
				End	P10	1st	R11			
141229	37	800ft	101P	055	180	24.5	13.3	OFF		103/5
				End	R11	1st	P11			820/4PM
141353	38	800	101P	055	180					
				End	P11	1st	R12			
141554	39	2000	101P	055	180	22.0	12.2	OFF		125/4

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 572.....

Date 14 Oct 97.....

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Video Tape	
No.	Ends
FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE	y/n
HORACE recording to disc	y/n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
				Start R18					SS=3
144223	52	100	1018	180	23.1	14.3		OFF	060/6.
				End R18 / Start P18					
144402	53	100	1018	070	180	"		OFF	/
				End P18 / Start R19					
144537	54	800	1018	070	180	23.8	9.0	OFF	060/5
				End R19 / Start P19					5000ft
144728	55	800	1018						
				End P19 / Start R19				Run 20	
144937	58	2000	1018	070	180	20.9	6.5	OFF	070/6.
				End R19 / Start P20					10000ft
145102	59	2000	1018	070				OFF	/
				End P20 / Start R20				Run 21	
145232	60	3500	1018	070	180	17.8	5.8	OFF	085/4
				End R20 / Start P21					
145552	61	3500	1018	070					
				End P21 / Start R21				Run 22	
145726	62	5000	1018	030	180	14.4	6.8	OFF	060/4
				End R21 / Start P22					
145949	63	FLOSO	1013	030					

Video Tape
 No. 11
 Ends 1550
 FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE / n
HORACE recording to disc / n
SATCOM sending pos reports y / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr		Wind/ Sea st.
				START	R	2				
133452	19	1000 FT	1018	100	180	18.7	15.4	OFF		177/12
				End	R2	/	14.0 P2			
133752	19	1000	1018	100						
				End	P2	/	15.0 P3			
133924	20	800 FT	1018	100	180	19.2	15.0	OFF		212/3
				End	R3	/	15.0 P3		500 FPM	
134203	21	500 FT	1018	100				OFF		
				End	P3	/	14.0 R4			
134343	22	2000 FT	1018	110	180	21.1	14.0	OFF		154/15
				End	R4	/	13.0 P4			
13473P	23	2000	1018	100	180	20.7	13.0	OFF		173/0
				End	P4	/	8.4 R5			
134941	24	4000	1018	100	180	17.5	8.4	OFF		161/9
				End	R5	/	10.0 P5			
135206	25	4000	1018	100	180			OFF		
				End	P5	/	9.1 R6			
135302	26	5000	1018	100	180	14.7	9.1	OFF		161/0
				End	R6	/	10.0 P6			
135520	27	5000	1018							
		40		End	P6	/	10.0 R7			
135620	28	4000	1018	100	180	17.4	10.0	OFF		155

Video Tape

No. 1550
Ends

FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	50 30.01	50° 34.88'N
Long	000 54.41E	0° 39.60'E
Time	141841	142019
Status	OK	NAV.

DRS recording to HORACE y/n

HORACE recording to disc y/n

SATCOM sending pos reports /n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
				Encl	R12	1	Start P12		1050 fpm
141717	40	2000	1018	050	180			OFF	
				Encl	P12	1	Start R	13.	106/3
141848	41	3500	1018	050	180	18.5	6.4	OFF	
				Encl	R13	1	Start	P13.	1000 fpm
142040	42	3500	1018					OFF	1
				Encl	P13	1	Start R14		
142205	43	5000	1018	055	180	14.6	6.1	OFF	073/2
				Encl	R14	1	Start	P14.	1000 fpm
142616	44	5000	1018	055	180			OFF	1
				Encl	P14	1	Start	R15	
142742	45	3500	1018	050	180	17.9	7.5	OFF	112/1
				Encl	R15	1	Start	P15	
143322	46	3500	1018	050	180	18.0	5.6	OFF	085/2
				Encl	P15	1	Start	R16.	
143451	47	2000	1018	070	180	22.0	7.8	OFF	082/3
				Encl	R16	1	Start	P16	5000 ft
143631	48	2000	1018	070	180	2			
				Encl	P16	1	Start	R17	
143841	49	2000	1018	070	180	24.6	8.4	OFF	065/6
				Encl	R17	1	Start	P17	
144015	50	2000	1018	070	180				
				Encl	P17				
144203	51	5000	1018	070	185	23	14	OFF	

Video Tape
No. Ends
FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE	y/n
HORACE recording to disc	y/n
SATCOM sending pos reports	y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr		Wind/ Sea st.
				End	P22	/	Start	R23		
150249	64	2000	1020	030	180	22.0	6.0	OFF		
				End	R23	/	Start	P24		
150435	65	2000	1020							
				End	P24	/	Start	R24		
150632	66	800	1020	030	180	23.0	7.4	OFF		058/8
				End	R24	/	Start	P25		
150804	67	800	1020					OFF		
SATCOM	67	800	1020	030	180	22.3	14.0	OFF		
150945	68	50ft	1020	030	180	22.3	14.0	OFF		/
				Start	R25					SS-3
150955	69	100ft	1020	030	180	22.4	12.7	OFF		046/7
				End	R25	/	Start	P26		
151132	70	100ft	1020					OFF		
				End	P26	/	Start	R26		
151307	71	800	1020	030	180	23.7	8.5	OFF		070/7
				End	R26	/	Start	P27		
151453	72	800	1020							
				End	P27	/	Start	R27		
151717	73	2000	1020	035	180	20.4	7.2	OFF		091/7
				End	R27	/	Start	P28		1000/8
151902	74	2000	1020							

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 572.....

Date 14 Oct 97.....

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Video Tape
No. <u>41</u> Ends <u>1550</u> <u>FFC</u> / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	<u>52°40.58W</u>	<u>52°44.93</u>
Long	<u>3°55.73E</u>	<u>3°56.61E</u>
Time	<u>1521</u>	<u>1522</u>
Status	<u>OK</u>	<u>NAV</u>

DRS recording to HORACE	y/n
HORACE recording to disc	y/n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	<u>(y)</u> /n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr		Wind/ Sea st.
				End	P28	/	Start	R28		
152040	75	3500	1020	040	180	16.2	3.1	OFF		104/0
				End	R28	/	Start	P29		
152235	76	3500	1020							
152422	77	FLO50	1013	End	P29	/	Start	R29		
152422	77	FLO50	1013	015	180	13.6	-21.6	OFF		111/79
				End	R29	/	Start	P30		
152657	78	FLO50	1013	055				OFF		124/10
				End	P30	/	Start	R30		
152832	79	3500	1020	045	180	15.9	7.1	OFF		122/6.
				End	R30	/	Start	P31		
153020	80	3500	1020					OFF		
				End	P31	/	Start	R31		
153148	81	2000	1020	040	180	20.2	6.6	OFF		027/6
				End	R31	/	Start	P32		
153335	82	2000	1020	040						
				End	P32	/	Start	R32		
153617	83	500	1020	040	180	23.2	7.3	OFF		075/7
				End	R32	/	Start	P33		
153816	84	500	1020					OFF		

Video Tape
 No. #2
 Ends 1855
 (FFC) / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE y/n
HORACE recording to disc y/n
SATCOM sending pos reports y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
154011	85	5000	End	P33	/	stat	R35		95-3
154011	85	5000	1022	040	180	22.0	16.1	OFF	/
			Stat	R33					
154114	86	100	1022	010	180	22.2	16.2	OFF	063/7
			End	R33	/	stat	P34		
154249	87	100	1022					OFF	72/5
			End	P34	/	stat	R34		
154419	88	800	1022	005	180	23.4	5.4	OFF	92/8
			End	R34	/	stat	P35		
154636	89	800	1022	005	180			OFF	
			End	P35	/	stat	R35		
154852	90	2000	1022	005	180	20.1	5.1	OFF	046/6
			End	R35	/	stat	P36		
155122	92	2000	1022						
			End	P36	/	stat	R36		
155254	93	3500	1022	200	180	15.9	6.7	OFF	077/6
			End	R36	/	stat	P37		
160030	94	3500	1022	270	180	16.5	3.9	OFF	070/6
			End	P37	/	stat	R37		
160158	95	5000	1022	275	180	13.4	1.6	OFF	078/7
			End	R37	/	stat	P38		
160722	96	5000	1022	260	180	13.7	-0.3	OFF	97/4

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 572.....

Date 190897.....

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Video Tape
No. Ends . FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE	y/n
HORACE recording to disc	y/n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr		Wind/ Sea st.
				End	P38	/	Start	R38		
160854	97	3500	1022	275	180	16.5	9.6	OFF		083/5
				End	R38	/	Start	P39		
161115	98	3500	1022	270	180					
				End	P39	/	Start	R39		
161247	99	2000	1022	275	180	20.5	11.2	OFF		109/6
				End	R39	/	Start	P40		/
161417	100	2000	1022	275						
				End	P40	/	Start	R40		
161631	101	800	1022	275	185	23.7	9.4	OFF		124/7
				End	R40	/	Start	P41		
161803	102	800	1022	275						
				End	P41	/	15.4			SS=2
161952	103	500 ^{ft}	1020	270	180	21.0	2+	OFF		133/7
				Start	R41					
162004	104	100 ^{ft}	1020	280	180	20.7	17.2	OFF		114/3
				End	R41	/	Start	P42		
162155	106	100 ^{ft}	1020	180	20.5	17.1	OFF			125/5
				Start	P42					
162349	107	100 ^{ft}	1020	165	180	22.2	10	OFF		143/8

Video Tape
No.
Ends
FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE	y/n
HORACE recording to disc	y/n
SATCOM sending pos reports	y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr		Wind/ Sea st.
				End	P42	/	Start	R42		
162525	108	800 ^{ft}	1020	165	180	23.7	5.5	OFF		146/8
				End	R42	/	Start	P43		
162740	109	800 ^{ft}	1020	165				OFF		/
				End	P43	/	Start	R43		
163007	110	2000	1020	160	180	21.1	7.6	OFF		141/7
				End	R43	/	Start	P44		
163118	111	2000	1020					OFF		
				End	P44	/	Start	R44		
163255	112	3500	1020	165	180	17.0	7.3	OFF		136/7
				End	R44	/	Start	P45		
163551	113	3500	1020							
				End	P45	/	Start	R45		
163720	114	5000 ^{ft}	1020	170	180	13.2	2.2	OFF		128/4
				End	R45	/	Start	P46		
163904	115	5000	1020							
				End	P46	/	Start	R46		
164037	116	3500	1020	165	180	17.2	5.0	OFF		141/6
				End	R46	/	Start	P47		22.7 ^o C in cargo hold
164742	117	3500	1020	165	180	17.0	0.5	OFF		120/5
				End	P47	/	Start	R47		
164913	118	2000	1020	165	180	20.4	9.3	OFF		42/5

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 572.....

Date 16th 1908 97.....

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Video Tape	
No.	1855
Ends	#2
EFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	52° 39.26N	52° 37.95N
Long	2° 21.63E	02° 24.12E
Time	1652	165417
Status	OK	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	y/n
HORACE recording to disc	y/n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr		Wind/ Sea st.
				End	R47	/	Start	P47		
165046	119	2000	1020							
				End	P47	/	Start	R47		
65311	120	800	1020	165	180	22.9	11.6	OFF		106 / 4
				End	R47	/	P47			
65456	121	800	1020	165	180			OFF		
65501	121	800	1020	165	180	21.2	13.4	OFF		
65701	122	50 FT	1020	180	180	21.2	13.4	OFF		SS=1 06 / 6
				Start	R47					
65709	123	100 FT	1020	180	180	22.5	11.2	OFF		059 / 5
				End	R47	/	START	P50		
165835	124	100	1020							
			WARM		FRONT					
			START	End	P50				500 RPM	
70010	125	50 FT	1020	275	180	21.2	14.6	OFF		62 / 7
				Adjust	P50				1000	
70205	126	1000	1020	275	180	22.4	7.6	OFF		074 / 5
				End	P50					
71955	127	FL100	1013	270	180	-9.1	-29.2	OFF		307 / 6
				START	R50					
72418	128	FL100	1013	265	240	3.3	-2.4	OFF		318 / 5

Video Tape
No. #2
Ends 1855
<u>FFC</u> / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	52°17.06N	52°15.50N
Long	0°45.03W	0°47.73W
Time	17 30	1730
Status	OFF	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) / n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) / n
	OPTIC
SATCOM sending pos reports	(y) / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.	
						Density correct.				
				End Run	50.					
				Climb	look up to	height.				
174056	129	FL100	1013	235	307	180	3.0	0.2	OFF	135/4
				Climb	up to	Height to	look for	Front		
				level	FL240					
175913	130	FL240	1013	300	180	-23.7	-52.5	OFF	194/4	
1800				Descend	to look for	FLIGHT				
				START	RUN	51				
181123	131	5000 ^{FL}	1012	225	180	12.8	4.1	OFF	173/12	
				H cal	P07					
				End	Run	51				
182558	132	5000	1012	220	180	12.2	11.6	OFF	178/13	
				Special	Descent					
				Start	R52					
182820	134	1000	1012	220	190	14.4	17.3	OFF	179/10	
184510				H cal	P10					
				End	R52					
184948	135	1000	1012	280	180	18.4	17.2	OFF	172/8	
				start	R53					
185026	136	1000	1012	270	180	18.8	17.5	OFF	171/7	
				End	R53					
190043	137	1000	1012	270	180	18.0	18.3	OFF	/	

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Flight No A ¹ 572.....

Date 19 08 97.....

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Video Tape
No. 572 #3
Ends 2100
FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	50° 56.36N	51° 09.76N
Long	6° 30.71W	006° 20.60W
Time	1900	1905
Status	OFF	NAV.

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y) n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr		Wind/ Sea st.
				End R 250						
10426	138	5000	1012.	START R 54	R 60	13.5	11.0	OFF		182/11
				End R 54						
13109	139	5000	1012	045	180	12.6	7.7	OFF		163/14
				Umb to	5000		Reciprocal			
13935	140	FLO80	1013	Start R 55	180	8.5	2.7	OFF		169/12
				End R 55						
14609	141	FLO80	1013	050	180	7.0	4.5	OFF		184/12
				Up	HORNE.					
1715				Land	RAF	LINE HAM.				
				Hold at		51	30 28 N			
02251				Date	OFF	10	59.28 N			

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: 572

DATE: 19 / 08 / 97

MRF

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION: GPS OMEGA INU RADALT	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓		
THERMOMETERS: DI TEMP NDI TEMP ICTP HEIMANN HYGROMETERS: GEN. EASTERN TWC FWVS J/W EXP. PITOT HEAD: STATIC PRESS. PITOT PRESS. GUST VANES	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓		
RADIOMETERS: UPPER CLEAR UPPER RED UPPER SILICON LOWER CLEAR LOWER RED LOWER SILICON MARSS SAFIRE DEIMOS ARIES	✓ ✓ 3NO2 ✓ ✓ 3NO2 ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓		
CHEMISTRY: OZONE ECGC NOX	✓ ✓ ✓		
OTHERS: CCN CLOUD PHYSICS CABIN PRESS NEPHELOMETER PSAP	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓		

4 units

- ✓ HORACE - Probe beeping.
H-W DU - 1st 2nd
NEZ. Hand Dist.

0403 HORACE FREEZE Halted. - GREEN LIGHT ON HORACE for ≈ 5 min. all displays locked up. Rebooted.

- 2 FFC - picture UFS.

3 HORACE Rear Van. Unable to display screen.

4 SATCOM - Not getting messages to EC40

5 NDI DI split of 0-90C @ 1710 passing FLOPO

6 No DRS data written to optic since 172042
But size of DRS.DAT.DAT files getting larger. and space on disk getting less.

7 A15 displayed dead at 1947. Could video switch to other displays, but no vertical line on A15 display.

8 One of the i/c leads on E Rack coms box UFS Marked.

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No A 572.....

Project TACIA.....

Date 190897.....

Tape No #1..... User CHEMISTS.....

Retention Period INDEF.....

* GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
1250	0000	FFC	Start Tape Climb out from RAF Lyneham
130242			
→ 132530		R1	FLOPO
132530			
→ 133435		P1	FLOPO - 50 ^{ft} .
133452			
→ 135302		SAW TOOTH 1 UP	R2 → P5 100 ^{ft} → 5000 ^{ft}
135302			
→ 140907		SAW TOOTH 1 DOWN	R6 → P9 5000 ^{ft} → 50 ^{ft}
140904			
→ 142205		SAW TOOTH 2 UP	R10 → P13 100 ^{ft} → 5000 ^{ft}
142205			
→ 144203		SAW TOOTH 2 DOWN	R14 → P17 5000 ^{ft} → 50 ^{ft}
144223			
→ 145726		SAW TOOTH 3 UP	R18 → P21 100 ^{ft} → 5000 ^{ft}
145726			
→ 150800		SAW TOOTH 3 DOWN	R22 → P25 FLO50 → 50 ^{ft}
150955			
→ 152422		SAW TOOTH 4 UP	R25 → P29 100 ^{ft} → FLO50
152422			
→ 154011		SAW TOOTH 4 DOWN	R29 → P33 FLO50 → 50 ^{ft}
154114			
→ 155122		SAW TOOTH 5 UP	R33 → R35 100 ^{ft} → 2000 ^{ft}
			End of Tape.

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No A 572.....

Project TACIA.....

Date 19 08 97.....

Tape No #2..... User CHEMIST S.....

Retention Period INDEF.....

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
155122 → 160158		FFC	P36 → P37 2000 ^{ft} → 5000 ^{ft}
160158 → 161952		SAW TOOTH 5 DOWN	R37 → P41 5000 ^{ft} → 50 ^{ft}
162004 → 163720		SAW TOOTH 6 UP	R41 → P45 100 ^{ft} → 5000 ^{ft}
163720 → 165835		SAW TOOTH 6 DOWN	R45 → R49 5000 ^{ft} → 100 ^{ft}
WARM	FRONT		
170010 → 171955		FFC	P50 50 ^{ft} → FL100
172448 → 174056			R50 FL100
174056 → 175913			FL100 → FL240
181123 → 182558			R51 5000 ^{ft}
182820 → 184948			R52 1000 ^{ft}

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No **A** 572.....

Project TACIA.....

Date 19 08 97.....

Tape No #3..... User CHEMISTS.....

Retention Period INDEF.....

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
125026 → 190043	0000	FFC	R53 1000 FT
140436 → 143109			R54 5000 FT
143935 → 144604			R55 FLOPO.
201715			Land RAF LYNHAM.

FUEL SUMMARY lbs

Start/Taxi : 1000 T/O Fuel : 49000

Plan Fuel : 27131 Plan Fuel : 27131

Diversion : 1500 Actual Reserve : 21869

Min Overhead : 5700 Hold Fuel Flow : 4500

Contingency : 543 Rsv Endurance : 4.51

Extra Fuel : 0 Flt Plan Time : 5.02

Reqd Start Fuel: 35874 Total Endurance: 9.53

WEIGHT SUMMARY lbs

ZFW : 98000

Ramp Fuel : 50000

Ramp Weight : 148000

Take Off Weight: 147000

Landing Weight : 119869

WAYPOINTS

EGDL 00513' N5130.6 W00159.4

BHD 112.70 N5023.9 W00329.6

SKERY N5000.0 W00310.3

ORTAC N5000.0 W00200.3

NEVIL N5000.0 W00021.6

HARDY N5028.3 E00029.5

51N01# CHANEL N5100.0 E00120.0

51#03E OSTEND N5130.0 E00300.0

52#04E TACIA N5255.0 E00400.0

53#04# TACIA N5330.0 E00440.0

54#04# TACIA N5405.0 E00440.0

54#01# TACIA N5405.0 E00140.0

52#02# TACIA N5230.0 E00230.0

DTYEST N5223.0 W00029.0

DTY 116.40 N5210.8 W00106.7

DTYWST N5157.0 W00146.0

EGDL 00513' N5130.6 W00159.4

OBSERVATIONS

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(c) RJCVC 1991

DATE 19 AUG 97	FTI No 01	FLT No A572	NAV A46RS
DEPARTURE AIRFIELD LYNCHAM			TAKE OFF TIME 1252
ATIS 'M' 25 GL 170/15 E 1000 H 1017 FS Ø -10 20 H 440'			
ATC CLEARANCE			

TIME	FIN 1012			IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT FL	QNH	GPS		RUN IDENT
	HDG	DR	G/S						LAT/LONG		
1302 ⁵⁰							F060	H 1017	5111.7	00232.8W	R1
1307 ³⁴							F060	/	—————	—————	R1
1325 ³⁰							F080	/	5008.8	00317.6	ER1/P1
1334 ³⁵									5000.9	00239.8	EP1.1/
1334 ⁵²							100'		5000.9	00238.5	R2
1337 ⁵²							600'		5000.6	00224.2	ER2/P2
1339 ²⁹							800'		5000.7	00216.6	ER2/R3
1342 ⁰³							850'		5001.0	00204.2	ER3/P3
1343 ⁴²							2000		5000.8	00156.4	ER3/R4
1347 ³⁶							2000'		5000.1	00137.5	ER4/P4
1349 ⁴¹							4000'		5000.1	00127.4	ER4/R5
1352 ⁰⁶							6000'		4959.9	00115.2	ER5/P5
1353 ⁰²							5800'		4959.9	00110.6	ER5/R6
1355 ²⁰							6000'		5000.0	00058.9	ER6/P6
1356 ²⁰							4000'		4959.9	00054.0	ER6/R7
1359 ⁴⁵							4000'		5000.4	00037.1	ER7/P7
1401 ⁴⁸							2000'		5000.2	00027.2	ER7/R8
1403 ³⁹							2000'		5001.5	00018.8	ER8/P8
1405 ³¹							800'		5005.2	00011.9	ER8/R9
1407 ¹³							800'		5008.5	00006.1	ER9/P9
1409 ⁰⁷							50/100		5012.1	00000.3W	ER9/R10
1410 ⁴							100'		5015.9	00007.2E	ER10/P10
1412 ²⁹							800'		5018.6	00012.0	EP10/R11
1413 ⁵³							800'		5021.4	00017.0	ER11/P11
1415 ⁵⁴							2000'		5025.5	00024.3	EP11/R12

ARRIVAL AIRFIELD	LANDING TIME
ATC CLEARANCES	
ATIS	

DATE	FTI No	FLT No	NAV
DEPARTURE AIRFIELD			TAKE OFF TIME
ATIS			
ATC CLEARANCE			

TIME	FIN 1012			IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT FL	QNH	GPS		RUN IDENT
	HDG	DR	G/S						LAT/LONG		
1417 ¹⁷							2000 [↑]	1017	5028.4	00029.4 ^E	ER12/P12
1418 ⁴⁶							3500		5031.6	00035.0	ER12/R13
1420 ⁴⁰							3500 [↑]		5035.9	00041.5	ER13/P13
1422 ⁰⁵							5000		5039.0	00046.8	ER13/R14
1426 ¹⁶							5000 [↓]		5048.4	00102.0	ER14/P14
1427 ⁴²							3500		5051.7	00107.0	ER14/R15
1433 ²²							3500 [↓]		5104.0	00127.8	ER15/P15
1434 ⁵¹							2000		5105.9	00134.8	ER15/R16
1436 ³¹							2000 [↓]		5107.9	00142.2	ER16/P16
1438 ⁴¹							800		5110.4	00151.7	ER16/R17
1440 ¹⁵							800 [↓]		5112.2	00158.4	ER17/P17
1442 ^{03/23}							50/100		5114.1	00206.1	ER17/R18
1444 ⁰²							100 [↑]		5116.3	00214.2	ER18/P18
1445 ³⁷							800		5118.1	00220.9	ER18/R19
1447 ²³							800 [↑]		5120.2	00228.9	ER19/P19
1449 ³⁷							2000		5122.6	00238.2	ER19/R20
1451 ⁰²							2000 [↑]		5124.3	00244.6	ER20/P20
1452 ³²							3500	1020	5126.0	00250.9	ER20/R21
1455 ⁵²							3500 [↑]		5132.5	00302.8	ER21/P21
1457 ²⁶							F050		5137.0	00305.4	ER21/R22
1457 ⁴⁹							F050 [↓]		5144.0	00310.1	ER22/P22
1502 ⁴⁹							2000		5152.9	00316.1	ER22/R23
1504 ³⁵							2000 [↓]		5157.9	00319.5	ER23/P24
1506 ³²							800'		5203.4	00323.2	ER24/R24
1508 ⁰⁹							800 [↓]		5207.7	00326.0	ER24/P25

ARRIVAL AIRFIELD	LANDING TIME
ATC CLEARANCES	
ATIS	

DATE	FTI No	FLT No	NAV
DEPARTURE AIRFIELD			TAKE OFF TIME
ATIS			
ATC CLEARANCE			

TIME	FIN 1012			IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT FL	QNH	GPS		RUN IDENT
	HDG	DR	G/S						LAT/LONG		
1509 ⁴⁵ / ₅₅							50/100	1020	5212.0 ^N	00328.9 ^E	EP25/EP25
1511 ³²							100'		5216.6 ^N	00332.4 ^E	EP25/EP26
1513 ⁰⁷							800'		5220.9	00335.3	EP26/EP26
1514 ⁵³							800'		5225.5	00339.5	EP26/EP27
1517 ¹⁷							2000		5231.6	00345.4	EP27/EP27
1519 ⁰²							2000'		5236.3	00349.5	EP27/EP28
1520 ⁴⁰							3500		5240.8	00353.3	EP28/EP28
1522 ³⁵							3500'		5246.2	00357.2	EP28/EP29
1524 ²²							FO50		5252.2	00358.1	EP29/EP29
1526 ⁵⁷							FO50		5300.3	00401.2	EP29/EP30
1528 ³²							3500		5303.9	00407.0	EP30/EP30
1530 ²⁰							3500		5308.1	00413.5	EP30/EP31
1531 ⁴⁸							2000		5311.4	00418.7	EP31/EP31
1533 ³⁵							2000		5315.9	00423.7	EP31/EP32
1536 ¹⁷							800'		5322.4	00431.9	EP32/EP32
1538 ¹⁶							800'		5327.2	00437.3	EP32/EP33
1540 ¹¹							50'		5331.7	00442.8	EP33/EP33
1541 ¹⁴							100'		5334.5	00444.2	R 33
1542 ⁴⁹							100'		5339.3	00443.5	EP33/EP34
1544 ¹⁹							800'		5343.9	00442.9	EP34/EP34
1546 ³¹							800'		5351.1	00441.9	EP34/EP35
1548 ⁵²							2000		5358.5	00441.0	EP35/EP35
1551 ²²							2000'		5406.1	00439.1	EP35/EP36
1552 ⁵⁴							3500'		5406.4	00430.2	EP36/EP36
1600 ³⁰							3500'		5405.6	00346.8	EP36/EP37

ARRIVAL AIRFIELD	LANDING TIME
ATC CLEARANCES	
ATIS	

DATE	FTI No	FLT No	NAV
DEPARTURE AIRFIELD			TAKE OFF TIME
ATIS			
ATC CLEARANCE			

TIME	FIN 1012			IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT FL	QNH	GPS		RUN IDENT
	HDG	DR	G/S						LAT/LONG		
1601 ⁵⁸							5000'	5000 1020	5405-6	00337-9	EP37/R 37
1607 ²²							5000'		5403.6	00307.0	EP37/P 38
1608 ⁵⁴							3500'		5403-8	00257.5	EP38/R 38
1611 ¹⁵							3500'		5403.8	00243.5	EP38/P 39
1612 ⁴⁷							2000'		5404-0	00235.0	EP39/R 39
1614 ¹⁷							2000'	1014	5404-2	00226.3	EP39/P 40
1616 ³¹							800'		5404-8	00213.8	EP40/R 40
1618 ⁰³							800'		5405-0	00205-1	EP40/P 41
1619 ^{52/20⁰⁴}							50'/100'	1020	5405.5	00155.0	EP41/R 41
1621 ⁵⁶							100'		5406.1	00143.8	EP41/P 42
1623 ⁴⁹							100'		5403.4	00137.4	P 42
1625 ²⁵							800'		5359.2	00139.7	EP42/R 42
1627 ⁴⁰							2000'		5353.0	00143.3	EP42/P 43
1630 ⁰⁷							2000'		5346.1	00146.9	EP43/R 43
1631 ¹⁸							2000'		5343.0	00148.4	EP43/P 44
1632 ⁵⁵							3500'		5338.4	00150.6	EP44/R 44
1635 ⁰¹							3500'		5329.7	00154.8	EP44/P 45
1637 ²⁰							5000'		5324.9	00156.8	EP45/R 45
1639 ⁰⁴							5000'		5319.6	00159.6	EP45/P 46
1640 ³⁷							3500'		5314.9	00201.8	EP46/R 46
1647 ⁴²							3500'		5253.6	00213.2	EP46/P 47
1649 ¹³							2000'		5249.2	00215.7	EP47/R 47
1650 ⁴⁶							2000'		5244.6	00218.4	EP47/P 48
1653 ¹¹							800'		5237.5	00222.4	EP48/R 48
1654 ¹⁶							800'		5232.5	00255.5	EP48/P 49

ARRIVAL AIRFIELD	LANDING TIME
ATC CLEARANCES	
ATIS	

DATE	FTI No	FLT No	NAV
DEPARTURE AIRFIELD			TAKE OFF TIME
ATIS			
ATC CLEARANCE <i>↑ F140 ↑ F240</i>			

TIME	FIN 1012			IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT FL	QNH	GPS		RUN IDENT
	HDG	DR	G/S						LAT/LONG		
1657 ⁰¹ /49							50/100	1020	5226.3	00227.6	EP49/R49
1658 ³⁵									5221.3	00227.4	EP49/ R49
1700 ¹⁰							50/9	✓	5220.1	00220.7	P50
1719 ⁵⁴							F180	-	5226.4	00227.0	EP50
1724 ¹⁸							F100		5225.4	00007.5	R50
1740 ⁵⁶							F100		5156.5	0139.0	EL50
1816 ²³							5000'	1012	5233.4	0453.5	R51
1825 ⁵⁸							5000'	-	5154.4	00529.7	R51
1828 ²⁰							1000'	/	5154.0	00531.4	R52
1849 ⁴⁶							✓	/	5057.7	00539.9	EL52
1850 ²⁶							✓	✓	5056.5	00541.7	R53
1900 ⁴³									VALY ARR of 5057.0	00633.0	EP53
1904 ²⁶							5000'	/	5107.8	00624.5	R54
1931 ⁰⁹							✓		5238.5	00442.3	EL54
1939 ²⁵							F080		5224.9	00504.9	R55
1945 ⁵⁰							F080		5242.9	00443.1	EL55

ARRIVAL AIRFIELD	LANDING TIME 1220
ATC CLEARANCES <i>R/W/S/L W 170/037km 1000/1017 Y420</i>	1250
ATIS <i>#50</i>	

DATE	FTI No	FLT No	NAV
DEPARTURE AIRFIELD			TAKE OFF TIME
ATIS			
ATC CLEARANCE			

TIME	FIN 1012			IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT FL	QNH	GPS	RUN IDENT
	HDG	DR	G/S						LAT/LONG	

ARRIVAL AIRFIELD	LANDING TIME
ATC CLEARANCES	
ATIS	

Message from Straits of Dover Satcom message to Paul Manko via N. Price
Flight v. interesting. High O₃ (up to 120 ppbv at 100 ft). NO_y up to 35 ppbv. CO over 300 ppbv.

We strongly suggest tomorrow's flight is another model validation exercise in ~~an~~ a similar area. Large discrepancies between model output and observations.

This experiment is strongly supported by SAP, KSL and other modellers.

Stuart + Kathy.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A572 Date: 9/8/97 Operator: DWA

Page 1 of 4

DRS 15 + 1 SEC

G.M.T.	PCASP			FSSP			2D-C			HVPS/2D-P			REMARKS
	Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	Reff	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m ³	Max Size	Habit	
30012													START OF DATA
30034		66	0.1										Run 1 8000'
31615		30	0.09										"
32255		200	0.15										
33243		180	0.1										Run A 2000'
33728		1100	0.1										END R4 START P
34941		450	0.1										END P " Run 5 4000'
35007		1070	0.1										END K5 START F
35206		500	0.1										START R6 END P 5000'
35520		800	0.1										END R6 START P6 5000'
35670		815	0.1										START R7 END P6 4000'
35945		910	0.1										END R7 START P7 "
40146		1170	0.11										START R8 END P 2000'
40330		1600	0.11										END K8 START P8 "
40531		2500	0.11										START R9 END P8 600
40730		2000	0.11										END R9 START R9 "
40907		4800	0.11										END P9 5000'
409		4800	0.11										START R10 100'
41064		2050	0.11										END R10 P.10 START
41270		2180	0.11										START R11 P.10 END
41394		1800	0.11										END R11 600 R.11 START
41864		1800	0.11										START R12 2000' P.11 END
4197		1700	0.11										END R12 " P.12 START
41948		500	0.1										START R13 3800' P.12 END
4200		500	0.1										END R13 " P.13 START
42205		1200	0.1										START R14 8000' P.13 END
42616		500	0.11										END R14 " P.14 START
42741		600	0.11										START R15 8500' P.14 END
42721		1000	0.11										END R15 " P.15 START
43251		1800	0.09										START R16 2000' P.15 END
43631		1500	0.09										END R16 " P.16 START
43841		2500	0.09										START R17 800 P.16 END
44050		1700	0.09										END R17 " P.17 START
44073		4000	0.09										START R18 700 P.17 END
44081		3800	0.09										END R18 1000' P.18 START

Flight No. A572

Date: 19/8/97

Operator: DWA

Page 2 of 4

G.M.T.		PCASP		FSSP			2D-C			HVPS / 2D-P			REMARKS
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	Ref	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m ³	Max Size	Habit		
144537	2100	0.09										START R19 800' P18/END	
												END R19 P19 START	
144937	950	0.08										START R20 P19 END	
145102	515	0.08										END R20: 2000' START P20	
145232	150	0.09										START R21 2500' END P20	
145552	1200	0.09										END R21 3500' START P21	
145720	800	0.09										START R22 5000' END P21	
145949	50	0.09										END R22 5000' START P22	
150149	4000	0.09										START R23 2000' END P22	
150435	2900	0.09										END R23 2000' START P23	
150637	2100	0.08										START R24 800' END P24	
150808	2500	0.08										END R24 800' START P25	
150945	2400	0.08										START R25 50' END P25	
150958	2800	0.08										START R25 100'	
151132	2170	0.08										END R25 " START P26	
151307	2100	0.08										START R26 800' END P26	
151453	2300	0.08										END R26 " START P27	
151717	200	0.08										START R27 2000' END P27	
151902	400	0.08										END R27 " START P28	
152040	1800	0.08										START R28 3500' END P28	
152225	2100	0.08										END R28 " START P29	
152422	75	0.08										RUN R29 5000' END P29	
152657	65	0.08										END R29 " START P30	
152832	2700	0.09										START R30 3500' END P30	
153020	2500	0.09										END R30 " START P31	
153146	2000	0.08										START R31 2000' END P31	
153335	1900	0.09										END R31 " START P32	
153411	1600	0.09										START R32 800' END P32	
153816	2000	0.09										END R32 " START P33	
154011	2400	0.09										" 80' END P33	
154114	2250	0.08										START R33 100'	
154209	2100	0.08										END R33 1000' START P34	
154410	1200	0.08										START R34 800' END P34	
154636	1050	0.09										END R34 " START P35	
154852	300	0.08										START R35 2000' END P35	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A572

Date: 9/18/97

Operator: DWA

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C			HVPS / 2D-P			REMARKS
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	Reff	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m ³	Max Size	Habit	
155122	1700	0.08										END R35 2000' START P36
155154	1200	0.08										START R36 3500' END P36
160030	500	0.1										END R36 " START P37
160158	275	0.1										START R37 5000' END P37
160722	300	0.1										END R37 " START P38
160854	1800	0.1										START R38 3500' END P38
161115	1650	0.11										END R38 " START P39
161247	1800	0.1										START R39 2000' END P39
161417	500	0.1										END R39 " START P40
161631	1600	0.1										START R40 800' END P40
161823	1500	0.1										END R40 " START P41
161952	3300	0.09										50' END P41
162004	"	"										START R41 100'
162156	3000	0.09										END R41 100'
162349	3000	0.09										100' START P42
162525	2000	0.08										START R42 800' END P42
1628	1250	0.08										END R42 " START P43
163007	980	0.09										START R43 2000' END P43
163118	800	0.1										END R43 " START P44
163255	1100	0.1										START R44 3500' END P44
163551	900	0.1										END R44 " START P45
163720	700	0.1										START R45 500' END P45
163904	600	0.1										END R45 " START P46
164037	600	0.1										START R46 3000' END P46
164742	400	0.1										END R46 " START P47
164920	1700	0.1										START R47 2000' END P47
165046	1600	0.1										END R47 " START P48
165311	2300	0.09										START R48 800' END P48
165456	1750	0.08										END R48 " START P49
165701	3000	0.08										50' END P49
165709	2500	0.08										START R49 100'
165834	2800	0.08										END R49 100' START P50
170010	3000	0.08										50' START P50
171230	50	0.1										1050' P50
171111												14500'

PCASP HEATER ON

PAN GC Log

GC Sample record			Flight Number: <u>AS72</u>					Operator: <u>[Signature]</u>					Date: <u>19/8/97</u>				
Sample No.	Time	Height	Channel 1					Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments	
			Optimisation = <u>6</u>					Optimisation = <u>6</u>				Optimisation = <u>6</u>					
Back Flush = <u>40.6</u>					Back Flush = <u>41.2</u>				Back Flush = <u>39.1</u>								
Flow rate = <u>4.7 ml/min</u>					Flow rate = <u>4.7</u>				Flow rate = <u>4.0</u>								
ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP					
#1	133530	100'	524	1371					537	2602			509	-61		Press around HZ Only. No. from GC	
#2	134350	2000'	525	1231					532	2440			509	-60			R24
#3	135026	3000'	524	1205					530	2307			507	-60			R25
#4	135826	5000'	522	1206					527	2301			504	-64			R26
#5	140942	400'	523	1352					524	2549			499	-60			R210
#6	141622	2000'	523	1279					521	2725			496	-65			R212
#7	142220	5000'	522	1165					519	2235			492	-65			R214
#8	143210	3500'	521	1219					516	2328			490	-62			R215
#9	143920	1000'	523	1323					514	2508			489	-61			R217
#10	144600	1000'	521	1320					511	2506			487	-64			
#11	145150	3500'	521	1213					509	2326			484	-65			R220
#12	150291	2000'	522	1275					507	2439			482	-66			R223
#13	151019	100'	521	1345					505	2546			481	-62			R225

PAN GC Log

GC Sample record			Flight Number: <u>AS72</u>					Operator: <u>JRS</u>					Date: <u>19/1/97</u>			
Sample	Time	Height	Channel 1					Channel 2				Channel 3				Comments
No.			Optimisation =					Optimisation =				Optimisation =				
			Back Flush =					Back Flush =				Back Flush =				
			Flow rate =					Flow rate =				Flow rate =				
ST	SP	DT	DP	BT	ST	SP	DT	DP	ST	SP	DT	DP				
#15	152056	3500	522	1215				502	2347			479	-66			R28
#16	152638	5200	521	1151				500	2294			477	-61			
#17	153000	800	521	1317				495	2514			474	-66			R32
#18	154420	800	520	138				497	2526			473	-65			R35
#19	155320	3500	520	1215				495	2343			472	-64			R36
#20	160110	3500	520	1215				495	2345			472	-63			R38
#21	161650	800	520	1319				495	2530			471	-61			R
#22	162445	800	519	1314				493	2517			469	-65			R42
#23	163000	2000	519	1272				492	2449			469	-65			R43
#24	163750	5000	519	1155				493	2247			469	-65			R45
#25	164930	2000	520	1274				493	2451			469	-61			R47
#26	165725	100	520	1341				493	2568			469	-61			R49
#27	181515	8000	520	1167				496	2324			468	∅			

ASXX 19 AUG 1997 02

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F 28**

ASXX EGRB MSLP ANALYSIS DT 0000 UTC 19 AUG 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

19 AUG '97 03:23 FROM MET ITOPS BRACKNELL TO 4886

** TOTAL PAGE: 001

Prepared and drawn to the Copyrighted Standard, Met Office, London. Met Office is a registered trademark.

19 AUG '97 15:35 FROM MET 1TOPS BRACKNELL 10 4806

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 0000 UTC 20 AUG 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Original scale 1:20m

METEOLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F 18

Prepared and drawn in the Cartographic Section, Met Office, London. ACAD:CF:150:0:John Phillips. METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE

19 Aug 1977 7+0

500-1000MB
500MB

--- THICKNESS DM.
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GAINT

VI 00Z TUES 19/ 8/97
TUES 19/ 8/97
VI 00Z TUES 19/ 8/97

19 AUG '97 04:03

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_2 PAGE. 001

PHEA50 EGR 0000Z
CHART 13
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION M 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03:50:35

20 AUG 1997 T+24

00Z TUES 19/ 8/97 VT 00Z WED 20/ 8/97 GMAIN T+ 24

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HEIGHT DM.

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MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_3 PAGE.001

19 AUG '97 04:05

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.50.48

CHART 13

PHEE50 EGRR 0000Z

FSXX 20 AUG 1997 05

FSXX EGRR 24H MSLP FORECAST VT 0000 UTC 20 AUG 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Original scale 1:20m

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F 28

19 AUG '97 04:28 FROM MET IPTOPS BRACKNELL

62

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DATA TIME: 190800 AUG 1997
 SCALE 1: 2 500 000 UK
 DATA CUTOFF TIME: 06:34

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03:32:57 CHART 27 PHDA30 EGRR 0000Z

J1 00Z MED 20/ 8/97 VI 00Z MED 20/ 8/97 GMRIN T+ 0 HEIGHT DM. 300MB

11 00Z MED 20/ 8/97 VI 00Z MED 20/ 8/97
 --- THICKNESS DM. 500-1000MB
 - - - HEIGHT DM. 500MB

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.48.45
 CHART 13
 PHEASO EGRR 0000Z

FRACIT 4-UP
19 AUG '97 13:45

12Z 19 AUG 1997

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX-2 PAGE. 003

**CAMBORNE
03808**

**HERSTMONCEUX
03882
AT 112**

**HEMSBY
03496
AT 112**

**ABERPORTH
03502
AT 112**

FACIT 4-UP
19 AUG '97 13:43

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MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_2 PAGE.002

FACIT 4-UP 19 AUG '97 13:41

12Z 19 AUG 1997

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_2 PAGE. 001

**LERWICK
03005
AT 23Z**

10	275	8
15	280	15
20	285	21
25	295	16
30	220	16
40	230	24
50	200	16
60	200	17
70	175	17
85	180	25
100		
MAX NIL		
TROP 191 -65		
	250	21
10	1654	
15	1594	
20	1214	
25	1071	
30	949	
40	766	
50	579	
70	314	
85	154	
100	16	
10 250.0		
15 180.0		
20 143.0		
25 122.0		
30 203.0		
40 167.0		
50 265.4		
70 297.3		
85 137.7		
100 562.7		
10 -33		
15 -57		
20 -61		

**DE BILT
06260**

10	360	12
15	555	14
20	005	12
25	105	12
30	095	8
40	055	6
50	020	4
60	325	4
70	120	10
85	105	25
100	085	14
MAX NIL		
TROP 267 -52		
	105	10
10	1655	
15	1393	
20	1206	
25	1060	
30	941	
40	742	
50	577	
70	314	
85	155	
100	17	
10 260.0		
15 187.0		
20 146.0		
25 119.0		
30 205.0		
40 168.0		
50 265.6		
70 300.1		
85 139.0		
100 565.7		
10 -55		
15 -52		
20 -50		

**LERWICK
07110
AT 23Z**

10	370	10
15	310	14
20	240	23
25	235	24
30	230	23
40	230	25
50	225	22
60	225	22
70	200	17
85	165	10
100	005	2
MAX NIL		
TROP 201 -59		
	240	23
10	1656	
15	1400	
20	1220	
25	1077	
30	953	
40	768	
50	580	
70	314	
85	153	
100	14	
10 256.0		
15 180.0		
20 143.0		
25 124.0		
30 205.0		
40 168.0		
50 265.6		
70 300.1		
85 139.0		
100 565.7		
10 -57		
15 -58		
20 -59		

**DE BILT
06260**

10	360	12
15	555	14
20	005	12
25	105	12
30	095	8
40	055	6
50	020	4
60	325	4
70	120	10
85	105	25
100	085	14
MAX NIL		
TROP 267 -52		
	105	10
10	1655	
15	1393	
20	1206	
25	1060	
30	941	
40	742	
50	577	
70	314	
85	155	
100	17	
10 260.0		
15 187.0		
20 146.0		
25 119.0		
30 205.0		
40 168.0		
50 265.6		
70 300.1		
85 139.0		
100 565.7		
10 -55		
15 -52		
20 -50		

**CAMBORNE
03808
AT 23Z**

10	350	9
15	305	14
20	265	13
25	200	13
30	190	17
40	210	19
50	200	20
60	205	19
70	210	27
85	195	21
100		
MAX	NIL	
TROP	207	-59
	210	13
10	1657	
15	1401	
20	1219	
25	1076	
30	953	
40	743	
50	579	
70	313	
85	153	
100	14	
11	256.0	
12	182.0	
13	141.0	
14	123.0	
15	205.0	
16	169.0	
17	265.7	
18	299.2	
19	138.4	
20	564.9	
10	-56	
15	-57	
20		

**HEMSBY
03496
AT 23Z**

10	345	11
15	355	15
20	345	10
25	345	7
30	355	39
40	080	11
50	345	12
60	005	4
70	030	3
85	085	6
100		
MAX	10263	
	345	60
TROP	221	-54
	355	54
10	1653	
15	1394	
20	1230	
25	1066	
30	943	
40	743	
50	579	
70	315	
85	155	
100	17	
11	259.0	
12	184.0	
13	144.0	
14	123.0	
15	200.0	
16	155.0	
17	262.8	
18	298.7	
19	138.7	
20	561.5	
10	-56	
15	-54	
20	-54	

**HERSTMONCEUX
03882
AT 23Z**

10	355	8
15	330	20
20	335	47
25	330	45
30	340	40
40	320	32
50	310	12
60	285	7
70	225	1
85	140	2
100		
MAX	NIL	
TROP	200	-58
	335	47
10	1656	
15	1398	
20	1216	
25	1075	
30	950	
40	746	
50	580	
70	316	
85	156	
100	16	
11	256.0	
12	182.0	
13	143.0	
14	125.0	
15	204.0	
16	166.0	
17	264.0	
18	300.2	
19	139.8	
20	564.2	
10	-55	
15	-56	
20	-58	

**ABERPORTH
03502
AT 23Z**

10	320	6
15	305	15
20	275	14
25	265	11
30	265	10
40	245	19
50	205	11
60	185	25
70	185	21
85	170	20
100		
MAX	NIL	
TROP	192	-61
	280	16
10	1655	
15	1398	
20	1216	
25	1075	
30	952	
40	747	
50	579	
70	313	
85	152	
100	14	
11	257.0	
12	180.0	
13	143.0	
14	125.0	
15	205.0	
16	168.0	
17	266.4	
18	298.8	
19	138.4	
20	565.2	
10	-56	
15	-58	
20	-59	

FACIT 4-UP
20 AUG '97 06:35

00Z 20 AUG 1997

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_6 PAGE.002

**STORNWAY
03026
AT 23Z**

10	265	8
15	240	17
20	190	31
25	220	30
30	210	25
40	190	33
50	190	32
60	185	33
70	190	33
85	180	38
100		
MAX	NIL	
TROP	197	-58
	190	31
10	1652	
15	1393	
20	1211	
25	1060	
30	946	
40	762	
50	576	
70	310	
85	150	
100	11	
10	259.0	
15	182.0	
20	143.0	
25	122.0	
30	204.0	
40	166.0	
50	266.2	
70	298.8	
85	138.7	
100	565.0	
10	-54	
15	-56	
20	-57	

**VALENTIA
03953**

10	305	8
15	280	17
20	270	19
25	205	43
30	210	43
40	210	29
50	225	17
60	195	17
70	195	17
85	185	16
100	150	14
MAX	NIL	
TROP	227	-32
	240	25
10	1657	
15	1401	
20	1215	
25	1070	
30	947	
40	762	
50	575	
70	309	
85	147	
100	9	
10	256.0	
15	186.0	
20	145.0	
25	123.0	
30	205.0	
40	167.0	
50	266.5	
70	299.6	
85	138.5	
100	566.1	
10	-55	
15	-55	
20	-51	

**BOULMER
03240
AT 23Z**

10	330	5
15	340	8
20	340	16
25	330	21
30	350	13
40	070	11
50	120	6
60	170	8
70	195	7
85	170	17
100		
MAX	NIL	
TROP	187	-62
	325	18
10	1654	
15	1396	
20	1216	
25	1073	
30	951	
40	767	
50	579	
70	315	
85	155	
100	16	
10	258.0	
15	180.0	
20	143.0	
25	122.0	
30	204.0	
40	168.0	
50	264.2	
70	298.8	
85	138.6	
100	563.0	
10	-55	
15	-58	
20	-60	

**LONG KESH
03920
AT 23Z**

10	290	10
15	270	14
20	220	27
25	220	27
30	200	21
40	195	22
50	180	21
60	195	22
70	180	26
85	175	29
100		
MAX	NIL	
TROP	209	-59
	225	26
10	1655	
15	1398	
20	1216	
25	1073	
30	951	
40	765	
50	576	
70	312	
85	151	
100	13	
10	257.0	
15	182.0	
20	143.0	
25	122.0	
30	206.0	
40	167.0	
50	266.5	
70	298.9	
85	138.3	
100	565.4	
10	-55	
15	-57	
20	-59	

FACIT 4-UP
20 AUG '97 06:33

00Z 20 AUG 1997

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_6 PAGE.001

A572 · 19-AUG-97 14:13:39 037 0 50.35 0.24 FC P

HDG deg T 50.	SPR mb 991.	PHGT k ft 0.6	TAS knots 187.	TAT C 24.4	DEW C 13.5	WIND deg m/s 099/5	
---------------------	-------------------	---------------------	----------------------	------------------	------------------	--------------------------	--

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	DEVICE	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572

19-AUG-97

14:58:39

062 Ω

51.68

3.07 FC P

HDG deg T 24.	SPR mb 844.	PHGT kft 5.0	TAS knots 206.	TAT C 14.5	DEW C -5.2	WIND deg m/s 065 / 4	
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A SELECT	B DEVICE	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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HDG degT	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
23.	857.	4.6	202.	15.1	-8.3	050 / 5

PRESS -9- 4.57 52.23

0.00 0.00 33.00 50.00 -5.00 100.00 133.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 15:15:57 072 Ω 52.48 3.64 FC P

HDG deg T 33.	SPR mb 973.	PHGT k ft 1.1	TAS knots 189.	TAT C 22.3	DEM C 7.4	WIND deg m/s 079/7	<i>via Arrivals E. Channel</i>
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OZONE MR 86.02 CO MR 156.00
ppb ppb

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT k ft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEM C	WIND deg m/s
9.	880.	3.8	196.	14.9	1.1	113 / 8

H202 NR 0998 2.67 333.33 2.33

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 15:24:18 076 Ω 52.87 3.90 FC P

HDG deg T 10.	SPR mb 845.	PHGT k ft 4.9	TAS knots 205.	TAT C 13.4	DEM C c-17.7	WIND deg m/s 111 / 8
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CO MR 102.00 OZONE MR 64.19
 ppb ppb

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 15:35:57 082 53.38 4.44 AS P

HDG deg T 41.	SPR mb 997.	PHGT k ft 0.4	TAS knots 190.	TAT C 23.6	DEW C 7.0	WIND deg m/s 072/7
---------------------	-------------------	---------------------	----------------------	------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

CO MR 144.50 OZONE MR 83.15
ppb ppb

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 15:38:33 084 Ω 53.48 4.56 FC P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT k ft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
40.	996.	0.5	188.	23.5	8.2	084 / 7

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 15:48:03 089 Ω 53.94 4.61 FC P

HDG deg T 359.	SPR mb 968.	PHGT kft 1.3	TAS knots 193.	TAT C 21.3	DEW C 3.9	WIND deg m/s 093/5	
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A SELECT	B DEVICE	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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A572 19-AUG-97 15:55:06 093 Ω 54.11 4.24 FC P

HDG deg T 272.	SPR mb 902.	PHGT k ft 3.2	TAS knots 184.	TAT C 16.3	DEW C 3.8	WIND deg m/s 071 / 5
----------------------	-------------------	---------------------	----------------------	------------------	-----------------	----------------------------

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 15:59:57 093 Ω 54.10 3.77 FC P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT k ft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
260.	902.	3.2	188.	16.7	4.4	065 / 7

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 17:09:18 126 52.42 1.41 FC P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT k ft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s	
279.	763.	7.6	206.	8.0	0.1	006/3	

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	DEVICE	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 17:15:42 126 Ω 52.46 0.81 FC P

H _{DG} deg 278.	S _{PR} m _b 597.	P _{HGT} k _{ft} 13.9	T _{AS} k _{nots} 227.	T _{AT} C -5.1	D _{EW} C -9.3	W _{IND} deg m/s 002/4
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CO MR 130.50 OZONE MR 70.82
ppb ppb

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 18:02:03 130 Ω 52.37 -3.74 FC P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
289.	394.	23.9	292.	-23.5	-52.5	193/5

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 18:05:30 130 Ω 52.47 -4.17 FC

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT k ft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
292.	489.	18.8	333.	-11.5	c-13.7	176/ 4

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	DEVICE	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 18:55:54 136 Ω 50.94 -6.12 FC P

HDG deg T	SPR m b	PHGT k f t	TAS k n o t s	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m / s
263.	979.	0.9	189.	18.6	17.9	170 / 8

POTE 333.59 OZONE MR 22.73
K p p b

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	-PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 19:00:42 136 Ω 50.94 -6.51 FC P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
263.	980.	0.9	186.	18.8	18.3	176/10

GE DEWP 18.32 TATND 17.54

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 19:11:54 138 Ω 51.65 -5.75 FC P

HDG ^{deg}T 39.	SPR $_{mb}$ 848.	PHGT $_{kft}$ 4.9	TAS $_{knots}$ 294.	TAT $_{C}$ 12.6	DEW $_{C}$ 10.9	WIND $^{deg} \ / \ m/s$ 193/10	
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	DEVICE	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 19:26:48 138 Ω 52.44 -4.89 FC P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT k ft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
38.	845.	4.9	197.	13.0	4.5	172/15

POTE K 319.30 INU MS 15.45

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A572 19-AUG-97 19:04:48 138 Ω 51.17 -6.34 FC P

HDG deg T 40.	SPR mb 850.	PHGT k ft 4.8	TAS knots 293.	TAT C 13.7	DEW C 11.8	WIND deg m/s 182/11
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POTE K 332.49 OZONE MR 31.56
ppb

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
<p style="text-align: center;">7 1 1</p>	<p>Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">1 of 3 2 of 3 7 3</p>	<p>Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">2 PLOT</p>	<p>SAFIRE log PAN CC CCN log CO MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">4 3</p>	<p>Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">→ 1</p>	<p>Instrument status forms RTD prints ← RETAINED 73-1 MISSION SCIENTISTS Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track</p>

TACIA_970819 (3D Model levels)

From 12Z 15/ 8/1997 to 15Z 19/ 8/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

TACIA_970819 (2D Model levels)

From 12Z 15/ 8/1997 to 15Z 19/ 8/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

TACIA_970819 (2D Model levels)

From 15Z 16/ 8/1997 to 15Z 19/ 8/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

TACIA_970819 (2D Model levels)

From 18Z 14/ 8/1997 to 18Z 19/ 8/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

A572 19-AUG-97

P1 (132530-133435) + P2-P5(133435-135302)

A572 19-AUG-97

P6-P9(135302-140907) + P19-P13(140907-142205)

A572 19-AUG-97

P14-P17(142205-144203) + P18-P21(144223-145726)

A572 19-AUG-97

P22-P25(145726-150945) + P26-P29(150955-152422)

A572 19-AUG-97

P30-P33(152422-154011) + P33-P37(154114-160158)

A572 19-AUG-97

P38-P41(160158-161952) + P42-P45(162004-163720)

A572 19-AUG-97

P46-P49(163720-165835) + P50(170010-171955)

A572 19-AUG-97

climb(174056-175913)

A572 19-AUG-97 R1 FL080 From 130242-132530 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:51

A572 19-AUG-97 R1 FL080 From 130242-132530 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:51

A572 19-AUG-97 R1 FL080 From 130242-132530 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:51

A572 19-AUG-97 R1 FL080 From 130242-132530 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:51

A572 19-AUG-97 R1 FL080 From 130242-132530 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:51

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 1369
 Mean 763.919
 Standard dev 18.9615
 Max value 817.898
 Min value 753.319

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1369
 Mean 281.089
 Standard dev 1.13870
 Max value 284.510
 Min value 280.045

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 1369
 Mean 275.579
 Standard dev 2.46920
 Max value 282.369
 Min value 271.551

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 1369
 Mean 43.7275
 Standard dev 13.9662
 Max value 86.6450
 Min value 30.5641

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 1369
 Mean 181.118
 Standard dev 304.525
 Max value 1361.86
 Min value 4.00013

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 1369
 Mean 6.262976e-03
 Standard dev 2.805563e-02
 Max value 0.228341
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 1369
 Mean 2321.39
 Standard dev 194.277
 Max value 2431.00
 Min value 1770.17

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1369
 Mean 50.7077
 Standard dev 0.308213
 Max value 51.1944
 Min value 50.1458

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1369
 Mean -3.09417
 Standard dev 0.242304
 Max value -2.55137
 Min value -3.35701

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1369
 Mean 7.55955
 Standard dev 0.908787
 Max value 10.0681
 Min value 6.03984

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1369
 Mean -1.27569
 Standard dev 1.17000
 Max value 0.840302
 Min value -4.48006

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1369
 Mean -4.766639e-02
 Standard dev 0.306082
 Max value 1.23203
 Min value -0.969925

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 1369
 Mean 7.73702
 Standard dev 1.05195
 Max value 10.7726
 Min value 6.29368

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 170.421

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 1369
 Mean 106.015
 Standard dev 2.56195
 Max value 111.252
 Min value 96.1649

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 204.028

A572 19-AUG-97 P1 FL080-50ft From 132530-133435 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:54

A572 19-AUG-97 P1 FL080-50ft From 132530-133435 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:54

A572 19-AUG-97 P1 FL080-50ft From 132530-133435 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:54

A572 19-AUG-97 P1 FL080-50ft From 132530-133435 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:54

A572 19-AUG-97 R2-R5,P2-P5 50'-5000' From 133435-135302 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:59

A572 19-AUG-97 R2-R5,P2-P5 50'-5000' From 133435-135302 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:59

A572 19-AUG-97 R2-R5,P2-P5 50'-5000' From 133435-135302 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:59

A572 19-AUG-97 R2-R5,P2-P5 50'-5000' From 133435-135302 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:59

A572 19-AUG-97 R2-R5,P2-P5 50'-5000' From 133435-135302 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:59

A572 19-AUG-97 R2-R5,P2-P5 50'-5000' From 133435-135302 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:59

A572 19-AUG-97 R2-R5,P2-P5 50'-5000' From 133435-135302 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:59

A572 19-AUG-97 R2-R5,P2-P5 50'-5000' From 133435-135302 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:59

A572 19-AUG-97 R2-R5,P2-P5 50'-5000' From 133435-135302 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 15:59

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 1108
 Mean 956.515
 Standard dev 49.4957
 Max value 1017.10
 Min value 849.584

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1108
 Mean 292.008
 Standard dev 1.60889
 Max value 294.193
 Min value 287.408

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 1108
 Mean 286.533
 Standard dev 2.70145
 Max value 289.304
 Min value 279.773

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 1108
 Mean 57.8903
 Standard dev 29.1924
 Max value 100.223
 Min value 10.0829

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 1108
 Mean 1614.69
 Standard dev 730.810
 Max value 3441.87
 Min value 183.477

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 1108
 Mean 1.570892e-02
 Standard dev 3.778436e-02
 Max value 0.240759
 Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 1108
 Mean 566.601
 Standard dev 454.391
 Max value 1522.15
 Min value 19.7202

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1108
 Mean 50.0081
 Standard dev 6.605003e-03
 Max value 50.0179
 Min value 49.9992

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1108
 Mean -1.92689
 Standard dev 0.428801
 Max value -1.17470
 Min value -2.66247

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1108
 Mean 4.49864
 Standard dev 2.69071
 Max value 9.36679
 Min value -0.479942

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1108
 Mean -0.487506
 Standard dev 1.29723
 Max value 3.15047
 Min value -2.36557

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1108
 Mean -0.216372
 Standard dev 0.355274
 Max value 0.933105
 Min value -0.913910

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 1108
 Mean 4.83509
 Standard dev 2.45303
 Max value 9.62238
 Min value 0.507478

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 173.815

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 1108
 Mean 96.9211
 Standard dev 3.10778
 Max value 103.191
 Min value 91.2550

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 90.9414

A572 19-AUG-97 R6-R9,P6-P9 5000'-50' From 135302-140907 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:04

A572 19-AUG-97 R6-R9,P6-P9 5000'-50' From 135302-140907 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:04

A572 19-AUG-97 R6-R9,P6-P9 5000'-50' From 135302-140907 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:04

A572 19-AUG-97 R6-R9,P6-P9 5000'-50' From 135302-140907 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:04

A572 19-AUG-97 R6-R9,P6-P9 5000'-50' From 135302-140907 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:04

A572 19-AUG-97 R6-R9,P6-P9 5000'-50' From 135302-140907 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:04

A572 19-AUG-97 R6-R9,P6-P9 5000'-50' From 135302-140907 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:04

A572 19-AUG-97 R6-R9,P6-P9 5000'-50' From 135302-140907 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:04

A572 19-AUG-97 R6-R9,P6-P9 5000'-50' From 135302-140907 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:04

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 966
 Mean 924.854
 Standard dev 55.9644
 Max value 1017.57
 Min value 848.308

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 966
 Mean 292.860
 Standard dev 3.78070
 Max value 297.977
 Min value 287.186

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 966
 Mean 284.405
 Standard dev 1.67581
 Max value 289.794
 Min value 282.264

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 966
 Mean 87.2433
 Standard dev 20.6905
 Max value 118.967
 Min value 47.7404

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 966
 Mean 1581.07
 Standard dev 905.229
 Max value 5357.53
 Min value 183.477

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 966
 Mean 3.347080e-02
 Standard dev 6.032841e-02
 Max value 0.295321
 Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 966
 Mean 855.738
 Standard dev 511.433
 Max value 1522.15
 Min value 16.0032

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 966
 Mean 50.0416
 Standard dev 6.210078e-02
 Max value 50.2044
 Min value 49.9978

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 966
 Mean -0.536243
 Standard dev 0.348945
 Max value 9.575360e-03
 Min value -1.17470

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 966
 Mean 5.59215
 Standard dev 2.63696
 Max value 8.42406
 Min value -1.08250

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 966
 Mean -3.45735
 Standard dev 1.52647
 Max value -1.21659
 Min value -6.67242

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 966
 Mean 0.309647
 Standard dev 0.342046
 Max value 1.08437
 Min value -0.671059

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 966
 Mean 7.16063
 Standard dev 1.10733
 Max value 8.92809
 Min value 3.93241

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 148.274

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 966
 Mean 98.6045
 Standard dev 3.07869
 Max value 103.675
 Min value 88.4334

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 74.9477

A572 19-AUG-97 R10-R13,P19-P13 100'-5000' From 140907-142205 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:09

A572 19-AUG-97 R10-R13,P19-P13 100'-5000' From 140907-142205 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:09

A572 19-AUG-97 R10-R13,P19-P13 100'-5000' From 140907-142205 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:09

A572 19-AUG-97 R10-R13,P19-P13 100'-5000' From 140907-142205 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:09

A572 19-AUG-97 R10-R13,P19-P13 100'-5000' From 140907-142205 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:09

A572 19-AUG-97 R10-R13,P19-P13 100'-5000' From 140907-142205 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:10

A572 19-AUG-97 R10-R13,P19-P13 100'-5000' From 140907-142205 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:10

A572 19-AUG-97 R10-R13,P19-P13 100'-5000' From 140907-142205 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:10

A572 19-AUG-97 R10-R13,P19-P13 100'-5000' From 140907-142205 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:10

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 779
 Mean 953.785
 Standard dev 49.1261
 Max value 1016.08
 Min value 849.194

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 779
 Mean 294.109
 Standard dev 2.65771
 Max value 297.433
 Min value 287.381

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 779
 Mean 284.614
 Standard dev 3.10168
 Max value 289.626
 Min value 277.844

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 779
 Mean 94.9751
 Standard dev 23.6105
 Max value 133.425
 Min value 52.1127

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 779
 Mean 1886.43
 Standard dev 1248.42
 Max value 5627.85
 Min value 140.232

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 779
 Mean 2.616568e-02
 Standard dev 5.840692e-02
 Max value 0.246101
 Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 779
 Mean 593.583
 Standard dev 452.819
 Max value 1522.15
 Min value 27.8977

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 779
 Mean 50.4202
 Standard dev 0.129494
 Max value 50.6514
 Min value 50.2044

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 779
 Mean 0.391168
 Standard dev 0.224487
 Max value 0.780770
 Min value 9.575360e-03

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 779
 Mean 1.34321
 Standard dev 1.29716
 Max value 3.48016
 Min value -1.89194

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 779
 Mean -4.40301
 Standard dev 1.42829
 Max value -2.49267
 Min value -7.48518

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 779
 Mean -0.329409
 Standard dev 0.320045
 Max value 0.451515
 Min value -0.864845

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 779
 Mean 4.82508
 Standard dev 1.27642
 Max value 7.61979
 Min value 2.74874

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 106.965

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 779
 Mean 97.3312
 Standard dev 2.33846
 Max value 101.355
 Min value 89.4176

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 47.7876

A572 19-AUG-97 R14-R17,P14-P17 5000'-50' From 142205-144203 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:15

A572 19-AUG-97 R14-R17,P14-P17 5000'-50' From 142205-144203 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:16

A572 19-AUG-97 R14-R17,P14-P17 5000'-50' From 142205-144203 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:16

A572 19-AUG-97 R14-R17,P14-P17 5000'-50' From 142205-144203 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:16

A572 19-AUG-97 R14-R17,P14-P17 5000'-50' From 142205-144203 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:16

A572 19-AUG-97 R14-R17,P14-P17 5000'-50' From 142205-144203 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:16

A572 19-AUG-97 R14-R17,P14-P17 5000'-50' From 142205-144203 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:16

A572 19-AUG-97 R14-R17,P14-P17 5000'-50' From 142205-144203 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:16

A572 19-AUG-97 R14-R17,P14-P17 5000'-50' From 142205-144203 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:16

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1199
 Mean 917.111
 Standard dev 53.6538
 Max value 1018.31
 Min value 847.373

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1199
 Mean 291.947
 Standard dev 3.57995
 Max value 297.715
 Min value 287.031

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1199
 Mean 280.596
 Standard dev 1.91619
 Max value 289.899
 Min value 276.261

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1199
 Mean 76.1645
 Standard dev 12.5214
 Max value 115.320
 Min value 53.3271

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1199
 Mean 1249.54
 Standard dev 822.116
 Max value 5028.51
 Min value 140.232

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1199
 Mean 2.602067e-02
 Standard dev 5.524598e-02
 Max value 0.240767
 Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1174
 Mean 914.461
 Standard dev 480.101
 Max value 1522.15
 Min value 14.8881

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1199
 Mean 50.9919
 Standard dev 0.174378
 Max value 51.2379
 Min value 50.6514

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1199
 Mean 1.41091
 Standard dev 0.382619
 Max value 2.09976
 Min value 0.780770

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1199
 Mean 7.613433e-03
 Standard dev 1.32962
 Max value 2.49440
 Min value -3.55434

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1199
 Mean -3.23441
 Standard dev 1.42008
 Max value -1.22921
 Min value -7.40559

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1199
 Mean 0.250491
 Standard dev 0.370545
 Max value 1.09271
 Min value -0.694046

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1199
 Mean 3.46909
 Standard dev 1.48663
 Max value 7.68452
 Min value 1.50571

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 90.1349

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1199
 Mean 98.7308
 Standard dev 2.96732
 Max value 107.483
 Min value 91.6979

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 54.8393

A572 19-AUG-97 R18-R21,P18-P21 100'-5000' From 144223-145726 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:22

A572 19-AUG-97 R18-R21,P18-P21 100'-5000' From 144223-145726 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:22

A572 19-AUG-97 R18-R21,P18-P21 100'-5000' From 144223-145726 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:22

A572 19-AUG-97 R18-R21,P18-P21 100'-5000' From 144223-145726 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:22

A572 19-AUG-97 R18-R21,P18-P21 100'-5000' From 144223-145726 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:22

A572 19-AUG-97 R18-R21,P18-P21 100'-5000' From 144223-145726 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:22

A572 19-AUG-97 R18-R21,P18-P21 100'-5000' From 144223-145726 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:23

A572 19-AUG-97 R18-R21,P18-P21 100'-5000' From 144223-145726 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:23

A572 19-AUG-97 R18-R21,P18-P21 100'-5000' From 144223-145726 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:23

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 904
 Mean 948.006
 Standard dev 49.4063
 Max value 1016.45
 Min value 845.422

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 904
 Mean 293.385
 Standard dev 3.05214
 Max value 297.654
 Min value 287.107

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 904
 Mean 277.650
 Standard dev 6.20744
 Max value 288.404
 Min value 263.555

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 904
 Mean 78.6086
 Standard dev 16.9032
 Max value 106.870
 Min value 48.8347

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 904
 Mean 1515.04
 Standard dev 1055.28
 Max value 4288.55
 Min value 14.2614

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 904
 Mean 2.665926e-02
 Standard dev 5.638256e-02
 Max value 0.240759
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 904
 Mean 567.042
 Standard dev 436.044
 Max value 1501.30
 Min value -26.5654

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 904
 Mean 51.3939
 Standard dev 9.876424e-02
 Max value 51.6186
 Min value 51.2439

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 904
 Mean 2.65253
 Standard dev 0.299894
 Max value 3.09056
 Min value 2.12308

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 904
 Mean -1.43894
 Standard dev 1.12435
 Max value 1.28338
 Min value -3.45448

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 904
 Mean -5.06394
 Standard dev 0.869347
 Max value -2.83745
 Min value -7.08418

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 904
 Mean -0.319221
 Standard dev 0.311536
 Max value 0.489754
 Min value -1.04241

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 904
 Mean 5.37649
 Standard dev 0.908832
 Max value 7.38686
 Min value 3.21768

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 74.1373

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 904
 Mean 96.8688
 Standard dev 2.45567
 Max value 104.127
 Min value 91.3179

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 58.2156

A572 19-AUG-97 R22-R24,P22-P25 FL050-50' From 145726-150945 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:26

A572 19-AUG-97 R22-R24,P22-P25 FL050-50' From 145726-150945 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:27

A572 19-AUG-97 R22-R24,P22-P25 FL050-50' From 145726-150945 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:27

A572 19-AUG-97 R22-R24,P22-P25 FL050-50' From 145726-150945 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:27

A572 19-AUG-97 R22-R24,P22-P25 FL050-50' From 145726-150945 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:27

A572 19-AUG-97 R22-R24,P22-P25 FL050-50' From 145726-150945 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:27

A572 19-AUG-97 R22-R24,P22-P25 FL050-50' From 145726-150945 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:27

A572 19-AUG-97 R22-R24,P22-P25 FL050-50' From 145726-150945 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:27

A572 19-AUG-97 R22-R24,P22-P25 FL050-50' From 145726-150945 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:27

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 740
 Mean 933.913
 Standard dev 59.4534
 Max value 1018.83
 Min value 843.195

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 740
 Mean 292.422
 Standard dev 3.67042
 Max value 297.523
 Min value 287.057

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 740
 Mean 277.167
 Standard dev 6.82071
 Max value 288.870
 Min value 263.747

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 740
 Mean 78.9968
 Standard dev 15.9519
 Max value 99.6696
 Min value 47.4239

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 740
 Mean 2229.89
 Standard dev 1387.63
 Max value 4971.29
 Min value 28.0073

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 740
 Mean 5.956786e-02
 Standard dev 8.430707e-02
 Max value 0.447486
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 740
 Mean 696.235
 Standard dev 534.877
 Max value 1522.79
 Min value -46.3261

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 740
 Mean 51.9167
 Standard dev 0.169368
 Max value 52.2017
 Min value 51.6186

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 740
 Mean 3.29229
 Standard dev 0.113580
 Max value 3.48324
 Min value 3.09056

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 740
 Mean -1.92915
 Standard dev 2.09443
 Max value 2.67641
 Min value -5.32584

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 740
 Mean -4.84167
 Standard dev 1.04860
 Max value -3.05115
 Min value -6.60847

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 740
 Mean 0.446580
 Standard dev 0.516530
 Max value 1.41376
 Min value -0.548500

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 740
 Mean 5.53388
 Standard dev 1.42161
 Max value 7.97526
 Min value 3.44631

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 68.2753

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 740
 Mean 98.5398
 Standard dev 3.02963
 Max value 105.745
 Min value 91.7330

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 22.6184

A572 19-AUG-97 R25-R28,P26-P29 100'-FL050 From 150955-152422 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:32

A572 19-AUG-97 R25-R28,P26-P29 100'-FL050 From 150955-152422 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:32

A572 19-AUG-97 R25-R28,P26-P29 100'-FL050 From 150955-152422 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:32

A572 19-AUG-97 R25-R28,P26-P29 100'-FL050 From 150955-152422 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:32

A572 19-AUG-97 R25-R28,P26-P29 100'-FL050 From 150955-152422 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:33

A572 19-AUG-97 R25-R28,P26-P29 100'-FL050 From 150955-152422 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:33

A572 19-AUG-97 R25-R28,P26-P29 100'-FL050 From 150955-152422 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:33

A572 19-AUG-97 R25-R28,P26-P29 100'-FL050 From 150955-152422 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:33

A572 19-AUG-97 R25-R28,P26-P29 100'-FL050 From 150955-152422 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:33

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 868
 Mean 952.473
 Standard dev 48.7282
 Max value 1017.25
 Min value 842.862

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 868
 Mean 292.971
 Standard dev 3.40052
 Max value 297.291
 Min value 285.924

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 868
 Mean 279.757
 Standard dev 5.29778
 Max value 287.140
 Min value 254.602

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 868
 Mean 82.6372
 Standard dev 6.33059
 Max value 88.9473
 Min value 58.1688

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 868
 Mean 2010.77
 Standard dev 630.427
 Max value 3297.86
 Min value 6.00019

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 868
 Mean 7.092306e-02
 Standard dev 8.350944e-02
 Max value 0.240751
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 868
 Mean 527.612
 Standard dev 430.521
 Max value 1526.01
 Min value -33.2457

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 868
 Mean 52.5273
 Standard dev 0.187684
 Max value 52.8721
 Min value 52.2088

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 868
 Mean 3.74817
 Standard dev 0.153855
 Max value 3.96798
 Min value 3.48846

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 868
 Mean -1.01964
 Standard dev 2.57605
 Max value 3.20118
 Min value -5.51077

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 868
 Mean -6.44191
 Standard dev 1.00857
 Max value -3.67952
 Min value -8.30928

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 868
 Mean -0.287186
 Standard dev 0.256469
 Max value 0.380035
 Min value -0.967316

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 868
 Mean 7.05993
 Standard dev 0.583123
 Max value 8.57669
 Min value 6.00556

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 81.0057

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 868
 Mean 97.4679
 Standard dev 2.54831
 Max value 105.359
 Min value 91.3131

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 23.7848

A572 19-AUG-97 R29-R32,P30-P33 FL050-50' From 152422-154011 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:39

A572 19-AUG-97 R29-R32,P30-P33 FL050-50' From 152422-154011 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 16:49

A572 19-AUG-97 R29-R32,P30-P33 FL050-50' From 152422-154011 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:39

A572 19-AUG-97 R29-R32,P30-P33 FL050-50' From 152422-154011 *Plotled* 9-Dec-1997 16:39

A572 19-AUG-97 R29-R32,P30-P33 FL050-50' From 152422-154011 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:39

A572 19-AUG-97 R29-R32,P30-P33 FL050-50' From 152422-154011 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 16:49

A572 19-AUG-97 R29-R32,P30-P33 FL050-50' From 152422-154011 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:39

A572 19-AUG-97 R29-R32,P30-P33 FL050-50' From 152422-154011 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:39

A572 19-AUG-97 R29-R32,P30-P33 FL050-50' From 152422-154011 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:39

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 950
Mean 934.017
Standard dev 57.5654
Max value 1020.73
Min value 842.374

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 950
Mean 291.648
Standard dev 3.78874
Max value 296.542
Min value 285.837

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 950
Mean 275.627
Standard dev 10.0685
Max value 290.445
Min value 249.812

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 950
Mean 76.9448
Standard dev 10.5401
Max value 91.6181
Min value 39.9005

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 950
Mean 1609.12
Standard dev 987.360
Max value 12554.5
Min value 6.00019

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 950
Mean 6.062236e-02
Standard dev 8.086130e-02
Max value 0.243397
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 950
Mean 694.397
Standard dev 516.539
Max value 1530.73
Min value -62.0806

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 950
Mean 53.2141
Standard dev 0.184705
Max value 53.5302
Min value 52.8721

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 950
Mean 4.32311
Standard dev 0.235196
Max value 4.71472
Min value 3.96798

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 950
Mean 0.979051
Standard dev 2.35625
Max value 5.43282
Min value -2.90057

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 950
Mean -6.43479
Standard dev 1.11009
Max value -4.87626
Min value -10.4909

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 950
Mean 0.403485
Standard dev 0.428426
Max value 1.33202
Min value -1.20403

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 950
Mean 6.90348
Standard dev 1.21891
Max value 10.4927
Min value 5.09449

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 98.6513

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 950
Mean 97.9490
Standard dev 2.76187
Max value 105.328
Min value 90.5558

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 34.2549

A572 19-AUG-97 R33-R36,P33-P37 100'-5000' From 154114-160158 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:46

A572 19-AUG-97 R33-R36,P33-P37 100'-5000' From 154114-160158 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 16:55

A572 19-AUG-97 R33-R36,P33-P37 100'-5000' From 154114-160158 *Plotted* 9-Dec-1997 16:46

A572 19-AUG-97 R33-R36,P33-P37 100'-5000' From 154114-160158 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:46

A572 19-AUG-97 R33-R36,P33-P37 100'-5000' From 154114-160158 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:46

A572 19-AUG-97 R33-R36,P33-P37 100'-5000' From 154114-160158 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 16:55

A572 19-AUG-97 R33-R36,P33-P37 100'-5000' From 154114-160158 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:46

A572 19-AUG-97 R33-R36,P33-P37 100'-5000' From 154114-160158 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:46

A572 19-AUG-97 R33-R36,P33-P37 100'-5000' From 154114-160158 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:46

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1245
 Mean 941.967
 Standard dev 46.1384
 Max value 1019.45
 Min value 851.413

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1245
 Mean 291.808
 Standard dev 2.96339
 Max value 296.146
 Min value 286.258

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1245
 Mean 279.355
 Standard dev 3.70734
 Max value 290.020
 Min value 273.199

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1245
 Mean 73.4988
 Standard dev 9.24065
 Max value 92.1016
 Min value 56.3163

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1245
 Mean 1109.36
 Standard dev 561.548
 Max value 2731.46
 Min value 87.7685

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1245
 Mean 4.901149e-02
 Standard dev 7.437346e-02
 Max value 0.233164
 Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1245
 Mean 723.359
 Standard dev 420.514
 Max value 1522.15
 Min value 26.4109

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1245
 Mean 53.9771
 Standard dev 0.171891
 Max value 54.1168
 Min value 53.5773

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1245
 Mean 4.41517
 Standard dev 0.350541
 Max value 4.73745
 Min value 3.62938

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1245
 Mean -0.495083
 Standard dev 1.30199
 Max value 1.61720
 Min value -2.58808

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1245
 Mean -6.58079
 Standard dev 0.863207
 Max value -4.39241
 Min value -9.32893

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1245
 Mean -6.106175e-02
 Standard dev 0.259542
 Max value 0.543564
 Min value -0.876244

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1245
 Mean 6.72419
 Standard dev 0.880949
 Max value 9.35645
 Min value 4.39713

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 85.6976

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1245
 Mean 97.8915
 Standard dev 2.82828
 Max value 105.438
 Min value 93.6402

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 308.407

A572 19-AUG-97 R37-R40,P38-P41 5000'-50' From 160158-161952 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:52

A572 19-AUG-97 R37-R40,P38-P41 5000'-50' From 160158-161952 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 16:59

A572 19-AUG-97 R37-R40,P38-P41 5000'-50' From 160158-161952 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:52

A572 19-AUG-97 R37-R40,P38-P41 5000'-50' From 160158-161952 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:52

A572 19-AUG-97 R37-R40,P38-P41 5000'-50' From 160158-161952 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:53

A572 19-AUG-97 R37-R40,P38-P41 5000'-50' From 160158-161952 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 16:59

A572 19-AUG-97 R37-R40,P38-P41 5000'-50' From 160158-161952 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:53

A572 19-AUG-97 R37-R40,P38-P41 5000'-50' From 160158-161952 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:53

A572 19-AUG-97 R37-R40,P38-P41 5000'-50' From 160158-161952 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:53

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1075
 Mean 918.934
 Standard dev 57.8824
 Max value 1019.97
 Min value 850.479

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1075
 Mean 290.618
 Standard dev 3.93111
 Max value 296.821
 Min value 285.686

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1075
 Mean 280.503
 Standard dev 4.80265
 Max value 294.737
 Min value 272.098

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1075
 Mean 69.7513
 Standard dev 11.9130
 Max value 88.4452
 Min value 46.4106

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1075
 Mean 1328.15
 Standard dev 777.729
 Max value 4320.85
 Min value 115.168

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1075
 Mean 3.542076e-02
 Standard dev 6.451356e-02
 Max value 0.233149
 Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1075
 Mean 926.427
 Standard dev 525.780
 Max value 1522.15
 Min value 14.5164

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1075
 Mean 54.0765
 Standard dev 1.116987e-02
 Max value 54.0950
 Min value 54.0599

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1075
 Mean 2.76398
 Standard dev 0.496570
 Max value 3.62938
 Min value 1.91345

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1075
 Mean 1.43338
 Standard dev 1.61012
 Max value 5.28608
 Min value -1.01175

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1075
 Mean -5.73193
 Standard dev 0.896717
 Max value -2.42795
 Min value -7.66572

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1075
 Mean 0.334541
 Standard dev 0.389104
 Max value 1.00680
 Min value -0.589218

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1075
 Mean 6.13018
 Standard dev 0.851251
 Max value 7.68626
 Min value 2.69246

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 104.040

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1075
 Mean 99.0162
 Standard dev 3.15392
 Max value 109.252
 Min value 94.6853

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 269.840

A572 19-AUG-97 R41-R45,P42-P45 100'-5000' From 162004-163720 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:59

A572 19-AUG-97 R41-R45,P42-P45 100'-5000' From 162004-163720 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:03

A572 19-AUG-97 R41-R45,P42-P45 100'-5000' From 162004-163720 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 16:59

A572 19-AUG-97 R41-R45,P42-P45 100'-5000' From 162004-163720 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:00

A572 19-AUG-97 R41-R45,P42-P45 100'-5000' From 162004-163720 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:00

A572 19-AUG-97 R41-R45,P42-P45 100'-5000' From 162004-163720 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:03

A572 19-AUG-97 R41-R45,P42-P45 100'-5000' From 162004-163720 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:00

A572 19-AUG-97 R41-R45,P42-P45 100'-5000' From 162004-163720 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:00

A572 19-AUG-97 R41-R45,P42-P45 100'-5000' From 162004-163720 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:00

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1037
 Mean 961.361
 Standard dev 49.6864
 Max value 1018.20
 Min value 852.112

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1037
 Mean 293.118
 Standard dev 2.69999
 Max value 296.651
 Min value 286.356

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1037
 Mean 281.732
 Standard dev 4.35874
 Max value 290.606
 Min value 275.224

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1037
 Mean 70.8177
 Standard dev 11.0612
 Max value 103.517
 Min value 47.8551

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1037
 Mean 1518.15
 Standard dev 977.550
 Max value 4354.01
 Min value 261.490

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1037
 Mean 4.628971e-02
 Standard dev 7.268062e-02
 Max value 0.246093
 Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1037
 Mean 537.550
 Standard dev 452.308
 Max value 1522.15
 Min value 28.6411

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1037
 Mean 53.8205
 Standard dev 0.216974
 Max value 54.1040
 Min value 53.4153

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1037
 Mean 1.77809
 Standard dev 9.577652e-02
 Max value 1.94870
 Min value 1.61786

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1037
 Mean 4.46656
 Standard dev 1.52306
 Max value 6.74958
 Min value 1.43267

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1037
 Mean -3.80585
 Standard dev 0.632039
 Max value -2.31985
 Min value -5.16782

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1037
 Mean -0.173582
 Standard dev 0.289209
 Max value 0.634453
 Min value -0.916992

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1037
 Mean 5.96864
 Standard dev 1.23549
 Max value 8.35681
 Min value 3.06451

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 139.568

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1037
 Mean 97.0079
 Standard dev 3.71296
 Max value 106.971
 Min value 89.3304

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 177.202

A572 19-AUG-97 R45-R49,P46-P49 5000'-100' From 163720-165835 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:06

A572 19-AUG-97 R45-R49,P46-P49 5000'-100' From 163720-165835 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:08

A572 19-AUG-97 R45-R49,P46-P49 5000'-100' From 163720-165835 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:06

A572 19-AUG-97 R45-R49,P46-P49 5000'-100' From 163720-165835 *Plotted* 9-Dec-1997 17:06

A572 19-AUG-97 R45-R49,P46-P49 5000'-100' From 163720-165835 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:06

A572 19-AUG-97 R45-R49,P46-P49 5000'-100' From 163720-165835 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:08

A572 19-AUG-97 R45-R49,P46-P49 5000'-100' From 163720-165835 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:06

A572 19-AUG-97 R45-R49,P46-P49 5000'-100' From 163720-165835 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:06

A572 19-AUG-97 R45-R49,P46-P49 5000'-100' From 163720-165835 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:07

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 1276
 Mean 935.398
 Standard dev 52.6931
 Max value 1018.87
 Min value 849.609

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1276
 Mean 291.856
 Standard dev 3.10623
 Max value 296.390
 Min value 286.071

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 1276
 Mean 278.589
 Standard dev 4.10277
 Max value 287.182
 Min value 272.765

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 1276
 Mean 70.8023
 Standard dev 12.4339
 Max value 99.4827
 Min value 52.7241

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 1276
 Mean 1215.99
 Standard dev 887.512
 Max value 4229.20
 Min value 78.0812

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 1276
 Mean 3.169045e-02
 Standard dev 6.362535e-02
 Max value 0.238170
 Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 1276
 Mean 768.600
 Standard dev 478.903
 Max value 1522.15
 Min value 15.2598

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1276
 Mean 52.8831
 Standard dev 0.304133
 Max value 53.4153
 Min value 52.3541

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1276
 Mean 2.22634
 Standard dev 0.163998
 Max value 2.46328
 Min value 1.94870

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1276
 Mean 0.390274
 Standard dev 1.45278
 Max value 2.53127
 Min value -3.33460

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1276
 Mean -4.13202
 Standard dev 0.721589
 Max value -2.38525
 Min value -5.70193

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1276
 Mean 0.390799
 Standard dev 0.366011
 Max value 1.65897
 Min value -0.549355

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 1276
 Mean 4.38963
 Standard dev 0.765994
 Max value 6.35233
 Min value 2.86907

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 95.3956

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 1276
 Mean 98.4328
 Standard dev 2.43419
 Max value 104.748
 Min value 92.8942

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 163.877

A572 19-AUG-97 P50 50'-FL100 From 170010-171955 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:12

A572 19-AUG-97 P50 50'-FL100 From 170010-171955 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:13

A572 19-AUG-97 P50 50'-FL100 From 170010-171955 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:12

A572 19-AUG-97 P50 50'-FL100 From 170010-171955 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:12

A572 19-AUG-97 R50 FL100 From 172418-174056 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:17

A572 19-AUG-97 R50 FL100 From 172418-174056 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:17

A572 19-AUG-97 R50 FL100 From 172418-174056 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:17

A572 19-AUG-97 R50 FL100 From 172418-174056 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:17

A572 19-AUG-97 R50 FL100 From 172418-174056 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:17

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 999
 Mean 698.078
 Standard dev 1.16652
 Max value 700.864
 Min value 694.695

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 999
 Mean 275.668
 Standard dev 0.526538
 Max value 277.118
 Min value 274.206

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 999
 Mean 273.536
 Standard dev 1.63137
 Max value 277.442
 Min value 269.454

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 999
 Mean 72.8516
 Standard dev 5.14776
 Max value 86.2603
 Min value 56.7079

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 999
 Mean 606.583
 Standard dev 322.929
 Max value 4841.76
 Min value 73.8511

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 999
 Mean 40.2319
 Standard dev 100.307
 Max value 467.387
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 999
 Mean 3033.75
 Standard dev 13.1335
 Max value 3071.89
 Min value 3002.44

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 999
 Mean 52.2147
 Standard dev 0.136177
 Max value 52.4263
 Min value 51.9448

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 999
 Mean -0.958362
 Standard dev 0.431128
 Max value -0.113098
 Min value -1.64517

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 999
 Mean 1.86747
 Standard dev 2.10856
 Max value 6.77810
 Min value -3.27122

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 999
 Mean 0.182909
 Standard dev 1.81208
 Max value 4.43996
 Min value -3.92548

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 999
 Mean 0.324963
 Standard dev 0.872573
 Max value 6.20923
 Min value -3.04935

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 999
 Mean 3.07428
 Standard dev 1.33918
 Max value 7.08808
 Min value 9.624231e-02

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 185.594

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 999
 Mean 121.090
 Standard dev 16.2925
 Max value 152.492
 Min value 105.660

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 242.872

A572 19-AUG-97 climb FL100-FL240 From 174056-175913 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:23

A572 19-AUG-97 climb FL100-FL240 From 174056-175913 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:21

A572 19-AUG-97 climb FL100-FL240 From 174056-175913 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:23

A572 19-AUG-97 climb FL100-FL240 From 174056-175913 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:23

A572 19-AUG-97 R51 5000' From 181123-182558 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:25

A572 19-AUG-97 R51 5000' From 181123-182558 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:22

A572 19-AUG-97 R51 5000' From 181123-182558 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:25

A572 19-AUG-97 R51 5000' From 181123-182558 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:25

A572 19-AUG-97 R51 5000' From 181123-182558 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:25

A572 19-AUG-97 R51 5000' From 181123-182558 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:22

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 876
Mean 845.503
Standard dev 0.518746
Max value 847.519
Min value 844.544

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 876
Mean 285.832
Standard dev 0.394895
Max value 286.333
Min value 284.755

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 876
Mean 281.331
Standard dev 2.98074
Max value 285.089
Min value 274.798

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 876
Mean 28.4522
Standard dev 5.36451
Max value 38.9293
Min value 19.1733

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 876
Mean 56.2814
Standard dev 50.3646
Max value 353.355
Min value 5.00032

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 876
Mean 7.98159
Standard dev 15.2374
Max value 53.6755
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 876
Mean 1500.53
Standard dev 4.99821
Max value 1509.77
Min value 1481.11

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 876
Mean 52.2298
Standard dev 0.189186
Max value 52.5551
Min value 51.9142

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 876
Mean -5.18288
Standard dev 0.161949
Max value -4.89361
Min value -5.48383

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 876
Mean 11.6814
Standard dev 0.576397
Max value 13.0632
Min value 10.1474

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 876
Mean -1.35524
Standard dev 0.988938
Max value 0.809586
Min value -3.77722

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 876
Mean 0.236286
Standard dev 0.491082
Max value 2.31730
Min value -0.961227

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 876
Mean 11.7995
Standard dev 0.609377
Max value 13.1519
Min value 10.2527

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 173.382

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 876
Mean 103.923
Standard dev 2.64627
Max value 107.676
Min value 97.4356

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 209.493

A572 19--AUG-97 R52 1000' From 182820-184948 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:29

A572 19-AUG-97 R52 1000' From 182820-184948 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:25

A572 19-AUG-97 R52 1000' From 182820-184948 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:29

A572 19-AUG-97 R52 1000' From 182820-184948 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:29

A572 19-AUG-97 R52 1000' From 182820-184948 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:29

A572 19-AUG-97 R52 1000' From 182820-184948 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:25

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1287
Mean 978.027
Standard dev 0.334291
Max value 979.027
Min value 977.271

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1287
Mean 291.918
Standard dev 0.240113
Max value 292.502
Min value 291.520

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1287
Mean 289.993
Standard dev 0.416782
Max value 290.791
Min value 288.805

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1287
Mean 25.3537
Standard dev 3.02354
Max value 32.1862
Min value 17.5183

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1287
Mean 341.238
Standard dev 120.513
Max value 726.318
Min value 140.223

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1287
Mean 6.985095e-02
Standard dev 8.662128e-02
Max value 0.243405
Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1287
Mean 337.031
Standard dev 2.56221
Max value 343.288
Min value 327.305

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1287
Mean 51.4463
Standard dev 0.274218
Max value 51.8995
Min value 50.9608

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1287
Mean -5.72302
Standard dev 7.060076e-02
Max value -5.52575
Min value -5.82183

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1287
Mean 10.4258
Standard dev 0.883081
Max value 12.1503
Min value 8.35438

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1287
Mean -0.225761
Standard dev 0.589809
Max value 1.31567
Min value -1.78230

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1287
Mean 0.216612
Standard dev 0.236201
Max value 1.36177
Min value -0.389442

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1287
Mean 10.4446
Standard dev 0.887149
Max value 12.1566
Min value 8.36420

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 178.760

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1287
Mean 96.1796
Standard dev 1.64116
Max value 99.7363
Min value 90.9351

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 185.229

A572 19-AUG-97 R53 1000' From 185026-190043 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:31

A572 19-AUG-97 R53 1000' From 185026-190043 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:27

A572 19-AUG-97 R53 1000' From 185026-190043 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:31

A572 19-AUG-97 R53 1000' From 185026-190043 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:31

A572 19-AUG-97 R53 1000' From 185026-190043 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:31

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 618
 Mean 978.913
 Standard dev 0.581034
 Max value 980.043
 Min value 975.035

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 618
 Mean 291.453
 Standard dev 9.082898e-02
 Max value 291.622
 Min value 291.232

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 618
 Mean 291.111
 Standard dev 0.310078
 Max value 291.691
 Min value 290.325

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 618
 Mean 23.1965
 Standard dev 1.40070
 Max value 26.6334
 Min value 19.7305

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 618
 Mean 366.193
 Standard dev 242.802
 Max value 2350.64
 Min value 75.1270

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 618
 Mean 40.8285
 Standard dev 48.3430
 Max value 171.607
 Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 618
 Mean 326.632
 Standard dev 5.31365
 Max value 364.476
 Min value 318.384

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 618
 Mean 50.9428
 Standard dev 1.869756e-03
 Max value 50.9454
 Min value 50.9401

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 618
 Mean -6.12664
 Standard dev 0.247480
 Max value -5.69970
 Min value -6.55454

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 618
 Mean 9.56571
 Standard dev 0.616428
 Max value 11.6564
 Min value 8.37501

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 618
 Mean -1.51399
 Standard dev 0.528181
 Max value -0.319519
 Min value -2.78373

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 618
 Mean 0.239874
 Standard dev 0.217372
 Max value 0.962036
 Min value -0.306992

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 618
 Mean 9.69913
 Standard dev 0.616670
 Max value 11.7471
 Min value 8.60485

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 171.006

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 618
 Mean 96.1902
 Standard dev 1.88498
 Max value 101.462
 Min value 91.1590

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 269.611

A572 19-AUG-97 R54 5000' From 190426-193109 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:35

A572 19-AUG-97 R54 5000' From 190426-193109 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:30

A572 19-AUG-97 R54 5000' From 190426-193109 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:35

A572 19-AUG-97 R54 5000' From 190426 - 193109 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:36

A572 19-AUG-97 R54 5000' From 190426-193109 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:36

A572 19-AUG-97 R54 5000' From 190426-193109 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:30

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1604
Mean 845.481
Standard dev 1.33593
Max value 849.332
Min value 843.187

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1604
Mean 285.423
Standard dev 0.440935
Max value 286.923
Min value 284.651

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1604
Mean 283.293
Standard dev 2.22723
Max value 285.342
Min value 275.144

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1604
Mean 29.5312
Standard dev 5.10120
Max value 48.2767
Min value 22.0783

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1604
Mean 59.2891
Standard dev 77.9350
Max value 534.569
Min value 1.00000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 1604
Mean 3.07339
Standard dev 14.8130
Max value 272.424
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1604
Mean 1500.75
Standard dev 12.8714
Max value 1522.87
Min value 1463.68

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1604
Mean 51.9471
Standard dev 0.429931
Max value 52.6449
Min value 51.1295

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1604
Mean -5.47201
Standard dev 0.481302
Max value -4.70377
Min value -6.41098

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1604
Mean 12.8911
Standard dev 1.18149
Max value 15.2788
Min value 9.30438

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1604
Mean -1.42278
Standard dev 2.16584
Max value 3.49414
Min value -5.18394

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1604
Mean -1.403326e-03
Standard dev 0.374823
Max value 0.726143
Min value -1.57046

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1563
Mean 13.1693
Standard dev 1.21856
Max value 15.8845
Min value 9.55958

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 173.702

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1604
Mean 118.663
Standard dev 23.0107
Max value 153.688
Min value 96.5303

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 34.9021

A572 19-AUG-97 R55 FL080 From 193935-194609 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:37

A572 19-AUG-97 R55 FL080 From 193935-194609 Plotted 12-Dec-1997 17:31

A572 19-AUG-97 R55 FL080 From 193935-194609 Plotted 9-Dec-1997 17:37

A572 19-AUG-97 R55 FL080 From 193935-194609 Plotted 9-Dec

A572 19-AUG-97 R55 FL080 From 193935 - 194609 Potted 9-Dec-1997 17:37

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 395
Mean 753.674
Standard dev 0.512592
Max value 754.270
Min value 752.116

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 395
Mean 281.020
Standard dev 0.234357
Max value 281.406
Min value 280.295

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 395
Mean 276.531
Standard dev 0.800488
Max value 279.178
Min value 274.935

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 395
Mean 44.1683
Standard dev 3.19938
Max value 50.1710
Min value 34.1270

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 395
Mean 37.5081
Standard dev 36.5699
Max value 107.125
Min value 1.00000e-38

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 395
Mean 1.053202e-04
Standard dev 1.478382e-03
Max value 2.109370e-02
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 395
Mean 2427.24
Standard dev 5.42412
Max value 2443.74
Min value 2420.94

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 395
Mean 52.5822
Standard dev 9.583063e-02
Max value 52.7470
Min value 52.4170

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 395
Mean -4.88154
Standard dev 0.115838
Max value -4.67742
Min value -5.07988

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 395
Mean 10.3301
Standard dev 0.809858
Max value 11.8279
Min value 8.61138

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 395
Mean -0.297748
Standard dev 0.710658
Max value 1.42458
Min value -2.19707

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 395
Mean 0.343036
Standard dev 0.191263
Max value 0.990105
Min value -0.150429

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 395
Mean 10.3579
Standard dev 0.820119
Max value 11.8581
Min value 8.64898

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 178.349

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 395
Mean 108.084
Standard dev 1.57664
Max value 110.593
Min value 104.025

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 36.6496

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.

Cloud Physics

- **PCASP:** The Passive Cavity Aerosol Sampling Probe counts number concentrations (number per cm^3) of particles in 15 channels spaced pseudo-logarithmically over the diameter range 0.10 μm to 3.00 μm , to provide a particle size distribution over this range.
- **FSSP:** The Forward Scattering Spectrometer Probe is used to measure water droplets in the size range 0.5 to 47.0 μm diameter (cloud droplets). It has four range settings, each of which is divided into 15 size channels.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent and Ken Dewey (UK Met. Office).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (raw data). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Sandra Schmitgen (FZ Jülich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data (approx) converted to ppb using actual scale factor and offset. Instrument scientist: Graham Mills (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters (NO, NO₂, NO_{y1}, NO₂₂) were recorded on MRF's data recording system and are plotted in bits. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section) to see when these were filled. Analysis carried out at NILU.
- **CO:** Approximate data in ppb from the DRS. Instrument scientist: Sandra Schmitgen (fz-Jülich).

ARASF

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